

Investigating the Dark Matter and Dark Energy Problem with Linearized General Relativity

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Abstract: The dark matter problem stands as a pivotal enigma in modern astrophysics and cosmology. This paper delves into the heart of this mystery, seeking to redefine our understanding of dark matter by examining it through the lens of the low velocity $v \ll c$ approximation of the Relativistic Theory of Gravity which is shown to reduce in the Newtonian limit to Gravitodynamics as well as mathematical modeling of the error term between the theory and observed data for fitting the force functions.

The simplest case of all the possible N-body solutions [1] for the mass distribution in a galaxy [2] is discussed and the implication from stability as well as galaxies which are known to have stellar orbits which are nearly circular [3] with eccentricity $\epsilon = 0$ and $a = \frac{v^2}{r} = \omega r$ and speed relative to the central object $v = \sqrt{\frac{GM}{r}} = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{r}}$. This paper is primarily concerned with the mathematical model and analytic derivations and representations of dark matter as well as the basic theoretical physics for the phenomena of Gravitodynamics [4] and the relationship to the theory of General Relativity in the Newtonian approximation of the field equations and geodesic equations [5]. Another main purpose of this paper is to bring forth as many possible mathematical models that can solve the dark matter problem and to consider them as potential sources for the additional force terms found by observational data [6].

By determining the error function one can determine the values of the dark matter force functions and the dark matter gravitational field. Using this data one can plot the fields produced by the error function and compare this field to the field produced by the theory to make inferences about the nature of the matter causing the force. Therefore, the error function can be used on galactic rotation curves, the dark matter map, and gravitational lensing data to make inferences about the density distribution for the dark matter ρ_{DM} , whether it be baryonic or Dark Matter made up of a completely different nature the mathematical effects it has on visible matter can be stated and the fields of any such matter distribution can be plotted as they interact with the visible matter. The error function for each case should be used in each case to determine the total differential in forces as a basis for the model that describes the observed galactic dynamics [7]. There is established computational toolkits for galactic dynamics [8].

Such characteristics are independent of the modeling of the field effects thus theoretically the error function between the theory and observations should produce a solid foundation for which the additional terms can be constructed. After the numerical approximations of the functions are made then a theory could be made to fit to the discrepancy for each case. Each case of the N-body problem is different so each type of discrepancy for each galaxy is different but the same fundamental underlying fact is true that the geometry of the galaxy is produced by the initial conditions to the N-body problem and therefore the initial conditions to the galaxy N-body problem determine the geometry or shape of the galaxy. Because the Gravitational Field is in the

Newtonian sense a 4-dimensional vector field with the 4th components being zero, and the gravitational field is produced by the distribution of matter, it can be stated that the initial conditions to the N-body problem produce the shape of the 4-dimensional Gravitational vector field. In this way, the plot of the 4d gravitational vector field of the error function force provides a path to calculate and plot the 4d mass density function. In relativity we know the statement that the Gravitational field is the 4d vector field is not technically correct since it is actually a Matrix field. This statement here primarily is that the Ricci curvature tensor contains part of the information of Space-Time and essentially implies the existence of a contracted general Gravitational curvature field tensor of the same rank. The Ricci curvature tensor is one such matrix field which is described with tensor calculus.

In adherence to the standard cosmological model, the comprehensive mass-energy composition of the universe is distributed as follows: approximately 5% comprises baryonic matter (observable matter), around 27% is attributed to Dark Matter, and roughly 69% is associated with dark energy. Consequently, the collective contribution of dark matter and dark energy represents approximately 85% of the total mass in the universe.

Galactic clusters

In 1933, initial suspicion of the existence of dark matter was from Fritz Zwicky [9], a Swiss astronomer. He was trying to measure the mass of a galactic cluster (a group of several galaxies) using two different methods. He attempted to infer this mass from the speed of the galaxies. Just like kids on a merry-go-round have to hold on to avoid being ejected, galaxies are held together in a spinning galactic cluster by the gravitational force provided by the matter it contains. If there were not enough matter to create this force, the galaxies would simply scatter. He found that many of the galaxies within these clusters were moving too rapidly to be gravitationally bound by the visible matter alone. He proposed the existence of "dark matter" to account for the additional mass required to hold these clusters together.

Zwicky measured the velocities of individual galaxies within galaxy clusters. He found that the galaxies in these clusters were moving at remarkably high speeds. According to the virial theorem, the galaxies should have been gravitationally unbound and dispersing, but they weren't. The high velocities indicated that there might be additional unseen mass providing the necessary gravitational attraction to hold the clusters together.

Data on galaxy cluster dynamics can be obtained from catalogs and surveys like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) [10] and the Chandra X-ray Observatory data archive [11], which includes X-ray observations of galaxy clusters.

Velocity curves of spinning galaxies

According to Newtonian gravity, the velocity of objects in a galaxy should decrease with radius because of Kepler's Laws and the Inverse-Square Law. Newtonian gravity builds upon Kepler's laws of planetary motion. Kepler's laws describe the motion of objects under the influence of a central gravitational force. One of these laws, Kepler's second law (the law of equal areas), states that a planet sweeps out equal areas in equal times as it orbits the central object. This law

implies that a planet moves faster when it is closer to the central object and slower when it is farther away.

Newton's law of universal gravitation describes gravity as an inverse-square law. It states that the force of gravity between two objects is directly proportional to the product of their masses and inversely proportional to the square of the distance between them. In the context of a galaxy, this means that the gravitational force, and therefore the centripetal force required to keep objects in circular orbits, decreases with increasing distance from the galactic center.

Given these principles, one might expect that in a galaxy governed solely by Newtonian gravity and visible matter, the velocity of objects in orbits should decrease with increasing radial distance from the galactic center, similar to how planets in our solar system move more slowly the farther they are from the Sun. In 1929 Edwin Hubble published the paper, "a relation between distance and radial velocity among extra-galactic nebulae," Edwin Hubble, Mount Wilson Observatory, Carnegie Institution of Washington, year 1929 [12], which showed a divergence between the Newtonian framework and the observational data.

Astronomers, including Jan Oort [13] and Horace Babcock [14], began measuring the rotational velocities of stars within galaxies in the 1930s and 1940s. They observed a puzzling anomaly: stars in the outer regions of spiral galaxies were orbiting at nearly the same speed as those closer to the center, contrary to what would be expected based on Newtonian gravity.

However, observations of many spiral galaxies reveal flat rotation curves, where the velocities of stars and gas do not decrease with radial distance. This apparent discrepancy between the predictions of Newtonian gravity and observed galactic rotation curves is one of the primary motivations for proposing the existence of dark matter. Dark matter, which is undetectable through electromagnetic radiation but exerts a gravitational pull, is hypothesized to provide the additional mass required to explain the observed flat rotation curves.

It was not until the 1970's that an American astronomer, Vera Rubin, measured the speed of stars in rotating galaxies accurately enough to convince the scientific community. She observed that stars in spinning galaxies were all rotating at roughly the same velocity, no matter their distance to the galactic center. This is in contradiction with Kepler's law that describes the rotation of planets around the Sun. Regarding the assumption of constant angular rotation in galaxies, it's important to note that this is an idealized assumption often made in simple models. In reality, the angular rotation of a galaxy can indeed vary with radial distance. While Newtonian gravity predicts a decrease in velocity with radius based on Kepler's laws and the inverse-square law, observations of flat rotation curves in galaxies suggest the presence of dark matter to account for the apparent stabilization of the visible matter for some radius. Rubin's observations provided compelling evidence for the existence of dark matter. Her work challenged conventional assumptions about galactic dynamics and played a pivotal role in solidifying the dark matter hypothesis.

In the 70s-80s, Rubin's work was confirmed in subsequent studies of various galaxies. It became evident that the discrepancy between observed and expected rotation curves was a widespread phenomenon, challenging the prevailing understanding of galactic dynamics [15].

From the 80s onward, the observed rotation curves of galaxies have played a central role in motivating theoretical efforts to explain the dark matter problem. Various hypotheses have emerged, including the existence of weakly interacting massive particles (WIMPs) as dark matter candidates [16] and the proposal of modified gravity theories like MOND (Modified Newtonian Dynamics) [17]. The Tully-Fisher law was discovered [18] and is what MOND is based on, which relates the luminosity or mass of galaxies to their rotational velocities.

In recent times larger studies have been performed to build databases such as "SPARC: Mass Models for 175 Disk Galaxies with Spitzer Photometry and Accurate Rotation Curves" by Federico Lelli, Stacy S. McGaugh, and James M. Schombert [19] presents a study involving a sample of 175 nearby galaxies. Observations of galaxy rotation curves often involve spectroscopy, which measures the velocity of stars or gas in a galaxy. Spectroscopic data provide the velocities of various components at different distances from the galactic center. High-resolution imaging allows astronomers to identify the spatial distribution of stars and gas in galaxies. This information is essential for constructing rotation curves. Radio telescopes are used to observe the radio emissions from atomic and molecular hydrogen in galaxies [20]. These emissions are crucial for tracing the distribution of cold gas, which contributes to the rotation curve.

Modern supercomputers are employed to process and model large datasets and perform complex simulations required for studying galactic dynamics although researchers continue to search for more efficient algorithms and techniques to simulate the dynamics on more cost effective super computers [21]. Rotation curve data for various galaxies are often available in astronomical databases and catalogs. For example, the HyperLEDA database [22] and the NASA/IPAC Extragalactic Database (NED) [23] provide access to galaxy rotation curves and related information.

Gravitational lensing

One striking dark matter detection technique is called “gravitational lensing” [24,25]. It is based on the way that large concentrations of matter (visible or dark) create gravitational fields strong enough to distort space-time. Light coming from a distant galaxy will bend when passing near a massive clump of dark matter. The galaxy will appear shifted, as if it resides at a different location than measured. The concept of gravitational lensing, the bending of light by massive objects as predicted by Einstein's theory of general relativity, was first proposed by Albert Einstein himself in 1915, although it was known by Einstein that Newtonian gravity deflects light as well [26].

The first strong gravitational lensing system, known as the Einstein Cross [27], was discovered in 1979. In this system, a distant quasar's light was split into four images due to the gravitational influence of a foreground galaxy acting as a lens. This observation provided early confirmation of Einstein's predictions and hinted at the presence of dark matter within galaxy clusters, which was required to explain the gravitational lensing effect. Subsequent observations in the 1980s and 1990s identified more gravitational lensing systems, both strong and weak. These systems included galaxy-galaxy lensing and galaxy cluster lensing events. The precise modeling of these systems required the inclusion of unseen mass components, often attributed to dark matter.

The Bullet Cluster (1E 0657-558) provided one of the most compelling pieces of evidence for dark matter through gravitational lensing. In this system, the visible matter and dark matter were found to be spatially separated during a collision between two galaxy clusters. Gravitational lensing maps clearly demonstrated the presence of dark matter, which had separated from the visible matter due to its lack of electromagnetic interactions.

Observations and data related to gravitational lensing can often be found in scientific publications and archives. Some projects, like the Strong Lensing Legacy Survey (SL2S) [28] and the Hubble Space Telescope's Frontier Fields program, provide publicly accessible data related to gravitational lensing. Gravitational lensing can be used to reconstruct the mass distribution of galaxy clusters, revealing the presence and extent of dark matter halos. This information helps constrain the mass and concentration of dark matter in clusters.

The COSMOS (Cosmic Evolution Survey) project [29] includes data related to weak gravitational lensing observations. Researchers can access catalogs and images of galaxies in the COSMOS field, which is used for studying dark matter distribution. CFHTLenS [30] is a survey focused on weak gravitational lensing. It provides data and catalogs of galaxies and lensing signals, aiding the study of dark matter in the universe. GREAT3 [31] is a challenge that provides datasets for testing and calibrating weak lensing analysis methods. It is valuable for researchers developing algorithms to study dark matter through lensing. The HST [32] has conducted numerous gravitational lensing observations. Researchers can access HST data archives to find images and datasets related to strong and weak gravitational lensing. The upcoming Euclid mission will provide extensive data related to gravitational lensing and the large-scale structure of the universe. Researchers can access Euclid's data archive for future studies on dark matter. DES [33] is a survey that includes weak lensing observations. Data releases from DES, such as its Science Verification and Year 1 releases, provide access to observations and catalogs used in dark matter research.

Cosmic microwave background

Astrophysicists can even infer how much dark matter exists by studying the cosmic microwave background. This fossil light has been travelling around for more than 13 billion years and now reaches us coming from all and no direction in particular. A map of the Universe has been given by the Planck satellite [34]. It shows hotter spots corresponding to where first dark matter then visible matter started forming lumps, providing the seeds for galaxies. Nowadays, scientists believe dark matter acted as a catalyst in galaxy formation.

The microwave background radiation can be decomposed just like sound from a musical instrument can be broken into harmonics. From the features of its "power spectrum", i.e. the amount of radiation associated to each frequency, astrophysicists can calculate the quantity of dark matter contained in the Universe. Data from CMB observations, such as those from the Planck satellite and the Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe (WMAP) [35], are publicly available through dedicated data repositories and archives.

The CMB radiation [36] is closely related to the dark matter problem and provides critical insights into the distribution and properties of dark matter in the universe. The CMB radiation is often described as the "baby picture" of the universe. It originated from a hot, dense phase of the cosmos, known as the "recombination era," when protons and electrons combined to form neutral hydrogen atoms. The CMB is the afterglow of the Big Bang, dating back to a time approximately

380,000 years after the universe's birth. It is a faint, nearly uniform background of microwave radiation permeating the cosmos. The patterns of temperature fluctuations in the CMB are not perfectly uniform. These tiny temperature variations, imprinted on the CMB, are the seeds of cosmic structure formation. They represent areas of slightly higher and lower density in the early universe.

Dark matter plays a significant role in the growth of these density perturbations over cosmic time. Because dark matter does not interact electromagnetically, it can clump together under the influence of gravity, forming "dark matter halos" [37] around which ordinary matter can collect. The distribution of dark matter influences the large-scale structure of the universe. Over billions of years, dark matter's gravitational pull causes the formation of galaxy clusters [38], superclusters [39], and cosmic filaments [40], which are observed in the cosmic web of the universe. The CMB temperature fluctuations are sensitive probes of the cosmic density field, including the distribution of dark matter. The statistical properties of these temperature anisotropies are influenced by the total amount of matter in the universe, including both visible and dark matter.

The CMB measurements, along with other cosmological observations, have been used to estimate the total matter content of the universe, often expressed as the "density parameter" Ω . Dark matter is a substantial contributor to this matter density, along with ordinary (baryonic) matter. The CMB also provides constraints on dark energy, another enigmatic component of the universe. The interplay between dark matter and dark energy in the cosmic energy budget is essential for understanding the overall cosmic dynamics. While the CMB appears remarkably uniform, it is not completely homogeneous. Small temperature fluctuations, or anisotropies, are present. These fluctuations represent tiny variations in the CMB's temperature across the sky, with some regions being slightly warmer and others slightly cooler. They arose from quantum fluctuations during the early moments of the universe. Over time, gravity amplified these fluctuations, causing regions with slightly higher density to attract more matter, eventually leading to the formation of galaxies, galaxy clusters, and larger cosmic structures.

Dark matter plays a pivotal role in this process. Being non-interacting and gravitationally attractive, dark matter acts as the scaffolding upon which ordinary matter, like gas and galaxies, congregates. The presence of dark matter halos provides the gravitational pull necessary for the formation of cosmic structures. The statistical properties of these CMB temperature fluctuations are crucial for cosmological studies. The power spectrum of the CMB, which describes how temperature fluctuations are distributed at different angular scales, contains valuable information about the overall composition of the universe, including the contributions of dark matter and dark energy. By analyzing the CMB's power spectrum, cosmologists can estimate the total matter density of the universe, typically expressed as the parameter Ω . This parameter includes both ordinary (baryonic) matter and dark matter. The precise measurement of Ω is essential for understanding the overall cosmic dynamics. The CMB, in conjunction with other cosmological observations like galaxy surveys and gravitational lensing, helps to constrain the properties of dark matter. These observations allow scientists to refine their understanding of the amount of dark matter in the universe, its distribution, and its interactions with other cosmic components.

The statistical distribution of temperature fluctuations in the CMB is described by the angular power spectrum. This spectrum shows peaks and troughs at different angular scales. The precise measurements of the angular power spectrum allow cosmologists to estimate cosmological parameters, including the density of dark matter. The positions and heights of the peaks provide constraints on the total matter content, including dark matter.

The Baryon Acoustic Oscillations [41] seen in the Cosmic Microwave Background power spectrum, whose only explanation is that there is a dominant mass component that does not interact with radiation (i.e., dark matter). The formation of large-scale structure, as measured by matter clustering, the strength of which requires at least 5x as much mass as can be seen in ordinary matter.

The Motions of Galaxies in Clusters

Observations of weak lensing in galaxy clusters such as the Bullet Cluster, which show that when clusters merge, the dominant mass component passes right through, while ordinary matter does not. It is known that in billions of years the Andromeda galaxy will collide with the Milky Way galaxy [42]. How does the gravity of galaxies within clusters affect one another? Initial calculations suggest that the forces are quite large from Andromeda, I found forces of the magnitude 10^{29} N with initial calculations using the distance between the galaxies and the total mass. This force should be more rigorously proven to be negligible since many galaxies reside within clusters. This is a small acceleration for such a large mass but over large time lines this results to large velocities approximately $\frac{145km}{s}$.

Cluster collisions:

One of the most complicated and dramatic collisions between galaxy clusters ever seen is captured in this new images of Abell 2744 [43].

Anomalies:

Researchers were surprised when they uncovered galaxy NGC 1052-DF2 [44] which is missing most, if not all, of its dark matter.

Black holes

Black holes initially emerged as plausible candidates for explaining the invisible mass [45], and they continue to be under consideration regarding the potential absorption of mass by these celestial entities. However, despite our awareness of numerous supermassive black holes, their sizes are notably modest in comparison to the galaxies they inhabit. For instance, the supermassive black hole situated in the core of our galaxy has a mass only a few million times that of our sun. In contrast, the mass of the entire galaxy is several trillion times the mass of our sun, with only approximately 10% of that mass being attributable to visible matter.

The disparity between the mass of black holes and the total mass of galaxies implies that a considerable number of black holes or a few exceedingly massive black holes would be required to compensate for the invisible mass. Nevertheless, if black holes were dispersed throughout the universe, their influence on visible matter would be conspicuously pronounced.

The origin of supermassive black holes remains uncertain, though it is established that they are not ubiquitously distributed within a given galaxy. The known mechanism for black hole formation involves the collapse of a highly massive star following a supernova event; however, such massive stars are infrequent and constitute only a small fraction of the 10% of visible matter

in the Milky Way. Consequently, the presence of black holes does not appear to account for the unseen mass, as their detection should be feasible.

Additionally, the notion of very small black holes [46] emitting radiation poses a counterargument. According to theoretical considerations, smaller black holes would emit progressively more radiation, potentially culminating in a sudden disappearance. Nonetheless, no observational evidence supports the existence of such small black holes, further challenging the hypothesis that they contribute significantly to the unseen mass.

Dark Matter map:

The inference of dark matter's existence is achieved through the examination of gravitational lensing effects on light originating from galaxies positioned behind concentrations of dark matter. By observing the distortion and warping of light around these dark matter clumps, physicists employ weak lensing measurements to construct maps depicting the projected mass density. An illustrative example of this methodology is presented in the paper titled "Direct measurement of dark matter halo ellipticity from two-dimensional lensing shear maps of 25 massive clusters," [47] wherein the authors detail the direct measurement of dark matter halo ellipticity based on two-dimensional lensing shear maps obtained from extensive observations of 25 massive clusters.

Utilizing contemporary knowledge and employing reverse engineering techniques, the weak lensing dark matter map is anticipated to exhibit a direct correlation with the principles of general relativity. Through meticulous comparison between the predicted map derived from relativity and the observed map, necessary adjustments can be made, or concealed variables identified. If galaxies are indeed the primary contributors to the gravitational lensing phenomenon, a comprehensive simulation of the total gravitational field throughout the universe can be established. This simulation, as opposed to assuming a particulate nature, contemplates the possibility of a field effect.

To discern the gravitational field map of dark matter, overlaid with existing dark matter maps and mass estimations, becomes pivotal in fitting the distribution to the lensing effects. This approach essentially mirrors the later-utilized error correction method, contrasting empirical data with theoretical predictions. The field plotted for dark matter equates to the field generated by visible matter, subtracted from the overall plotted field. The aggregate of these fields collectively manifests the total effect on tangible matter.

In substantiating the proposition that field perturbations or additional forces arise from the motion of galaxies, the derived total field map can serve as a numerical basis for determining accurate equations governing density profiles, mass functions, and velocity functions. The density distribution associated with dark matter, thus, may be numerically integrated as an input for mass distribution, facilitating the visualization of resulting gravitational fields attributable to matter.

Dark Energy

The expansion of the universe can be measured by measuring the vector field of expansion essentially obtained from considering N flat field equations and inputting the velocities of the objects. The Lorentz equations would imply that if the space is expanding between objects there would be points at which the space is expanding faster than the speed of light, so these velocities the farther we look eventually would reach a point of becoming approximately constant. I think this is potentially indicative that the infinity in one frame is not equal to infinity in another so the point at which this occurs in one frame is the same point at which in another frame there are complex coordinates if we select a point at infinity far beyond the initial system because then the

first system would be far isolated from the second system. It is possible that the 5th variable has to be used within the domain $\infty_1 < w < \infty_2$. That is, if the relativistic effect does not fully accommodate for all cases without adding additional dimensions to GR for a smooth transition between the two separated systems.

In principle a similar method used for dark energy should be able to be used. If we can obtain a plot of the dark energy distribution, we can use this data to plot the gravitational field of the dark energy, and ultimately the interaction with the visible matter from the error terms. We may not be able to determine the cause for the forces without looking at all cases but this method should give a possible path for which to create the necessary modifications for any theory of dark energy.

From CERN on Dark Energy, “It is distributed evenly throughout the universe, not only in space but also in time –in other words, its effect is not diluted as the universe expands. The even distribution means that dark energy does not have any local gravitational effects, but rather a global effect on the universe as a whole. This leads to a repulsive force, which tends to accelerate the expansion of the universe. The rate of expansion and its acceleration can be measured by observations based on the Hubble law. These measurements together with other scientific data have confirmed the existence of dark energy and provide an estimate of just how much this mysterious substance exists.

It is confusing to me that the space between objects could “expand” faster than light, but we learned that superluminal velocities are typically correlated to complex functions from the insertion of velocities larger than c into $\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$. This would imply that the regions of space which are expanding faster than light is potentially rich in the virtual energy density of the vacuum of space.

In the context of the Unified Field Theory [48] and the Zoom Operator, considering infinite zoom is essentially the same thing as considering the scale in which the universe which is almost infinitely large relatively to us and simultaneously the scale in which this universe is a singularity. A scale, or zoom can always be selected such that the current observable universe is a singularity. Using this fact, we can explore the expansion of the universe as a dynamical effect and observing the matter in the universe. The fundamental question we seek to answer is why is the universe expanding? We know that there exist this dark energy constant that essentially causes the acceleration of the real matter but why is this happening?

Consider the simple sketch representation on the next page:

If there was a singularity contained within the space (dx, dy, dz, dt) , we could theoretically consider the coordinates $(^{-\infty}dx, ^{-\infty}dy, ^{-\infty}dz, ^{-\infty}dt)$ zoomed in infinitely to see from the smallest scale possible what the large scale structure looks like, where from this perspective the infinitesimal dx appears infinitely large. We could consider the perspective in which no matter what time has passed, the universe always appears like a singularity: $(^{\infty}dx, ^{\infty}dy, ^{\infty}dz, ^{\infty}dt)$. After enough time has passed, the infinitesimals become functions (x, y, z, t) and the zoomed in scale coordinates where the universe which has a finite radius is $(^{-\infty}x, ^{-\infty}y, ^{-\infty}z, ^{-\infty}t)$ and in the scale where the universe is infinitely small $(^{\infty}x, ^{\infty}y, ^{\infty}z, ^{\infty}t)$. After some more time has passed the boundary for the observable universe changes to (X, Y, Z, T) and in the respective zoom scalings we have the pair of coordinates $(^{-\infty}X, ^{-\infty}Y, ^{-\infty}Z, ^{-\infty}T)$ and $(^{\infty}X, ^{\infty}Y, ^{\infty}Z, ^{\infty}T)$.

The universe in the large scale view may look like a black hole which has an event horizon in this scaling but in the small scale viewpoint where the universe is infinitely large is essentially the Schwarzschild solution where if there is any universe beyond this boundary would be attracted to the observable universe by gravity. So on the large scale it looks like a black hole but the small scale it looks like white hole in the coordinates $(^{-\infty}X, ^{-\infty}Y, ^{-\infty}Z, ^{-\infty}T)$. The solutions of Einstein's equations can be defined as a superposition of all scales for all timelines. The white hole forces are essentially the big bang forces that are causing the accelerating universe and apparent complex space-times which are superluminal speeds for space-time expansion thought to be dark energy. The solutions must be defined for all scales. There must be gravity outside our universe caused by our universe. It seems possible to interpret that we can plot the gravity and other fields outside the universe by motion of the matter using the relativity of zoom to relate inward gravity flow outward of the universe to the expansion inward. Is it true that all black holes are white holes in some frame where the Einstein equations considered for all possible zooms? Yes, but one must consider complex coordinate systems where for example, the singularity which initially appeared like a black hole evaporation and for some event, maybe the recoil of our universe off another universe in some sort of universe scattering or attraction, or that our universe lies in a sea of infinite universe

and for some reason or another there was a supermassive event that caused the matter to become a black hole which collapsed and our universe is the result of the collapse of such a super massive black hole [49]. I think the black hole collapse idea is something to consider as the responsible forces of the forces that caused the big bang. Whatever those forces are, they must be equivalent to the forces driving the expansion. My bet is that our universe is a part of a larger unseen system of universes. This thought experiment here depicts how one set of solutions evolve into another set of solutions over large enough time scales and suggests that the black hole solutions over large enough time scales evolve into other sets of solutions. This could easily be established by the fact that black holes emit and lose energy over time. Large time scales would lead to the eventual collapse of the Schwarzschild metric and transformation of the metric into a different solution. This is guaranteed by Hawking radiation. If the universe was once a black hole that collapsed, then this implies that the Schwarzschild solution evolves to the white hole solution from some frame over large enough timelines.

Stitching together solutions over all scales to produce the solutions to the Einstein field equations would imply that the Schwarzschild solution and the white hole solution together form the total solution to the equations. Is it possible that the superluminal complex space is only so relatively but outside of the universe the space is Real? What caused such a universal massive black hole singularity? It seems that the exterior gravitational energy in that instant is being converted to all other energies we see that have evolved in our observable universe.

If we generalize the notion of stability to all of space-time in the N-D coordinate space-time and allow zoom to operate over positive and negative infinity, this would imply that there may not be local conservation in the system which is a subsystem to a larger system if the subsystem has external influencing factors from the larger system. So theoretically the balancing of the universe would occur over all infinite scales so to include the structure of the universe on all possible scales including the possible external universes to the main universe.

Modified theories:

In addition to MOND there is Kaluza-Klein Dark Matter in Universal Extra Dimensions, as well as modified relativity theory. From the Unified field theory developed by extending the notions of Einstein's Unified Field Theory expect that there is a particle representation for the scenario even if there is no physical dark matter particle it could be virtually modeled since the virtual particles essentially could be seen as the field perturbations of space-time. Einstein originally proposed the existence of negative masses, which have the unusual property of being gravitationally repulsive. These negative masses can drive cosmic expansion and do not form light-emitting structures. Negative matter can be shown to be space-time inverted matter. Negative matter still has positive energies. In the modified unified field theory with generalized nested mathematical objects in 2N-dimensions with an imaginary value for every matrix and vector element is used to form differentiable Complex manifolds for space-time. Imaginary particles are used in the representation of virtual particles which produces the thought experiment of sending a pulse of light down the Imaginary axis. The energies of imaginary particles could be negative due to the squaring of the velocity in the kinetic energy term. This arises with peculiar definition of imaginary particles with Real mass but Imaginary velocities. The negative energy can be seen with: $E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{1}{2}m(iv_i)^2 = -\frac{1}{2}mv_i^2$. Cases in which this may be true is if v is superluminal

as shown from the relativistic energy equation $E = mc^2\gamma = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1-\frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$ where with $v > c$, $E \in \mathbb{C}$.

Letting a pulse of light travel down the Imaginary axis gives the equation: $E = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{1-\frac{(ic)^2}{c^2}}} = \frac{mc^2}{\sqrt{2}}$. The

logic was that the coordinate transforms necessary to view life from the perspective of a rapidly moving mathematical point that is smaller than the electron radius that has properties called charge, spin, mass, and a magnetic moment. So essentially the model is that the properties create the fields. In other words it seems possible that the Imaginary or this part of the virtual particle can have real energy. Superluminal velocities are physically impossible but seem rather to be the result of relativistic transformations of the space-time.

In this context, Complex matter is virtual matter. This it turns out is related to virtual photons. This is matter which has passed the boundary imposed by the speed of light. Imaginary matter can give negative energies. This matter has superluminal velocities in virtual space-time.

From the fact that there are gravitomagnetic terms not present in the Newtonian case, it can be inferred that there are additional terms in relativity case not present in Newtonian case. It should also be stated that the gravitomagnetic field is a relativistic phenomena of the gravitostatic fields or Newtonian gravity fields. This is not a modified theory of relativity but rather a modified theory of Newtonian gravity. The theory of relativity IS a modified theory of Newtonian gravity so we should first establish before we do create a modified theory that the relativity model does not already have the sufficient extra terms.

Other modified theories include Tensor-Vector-Scalar Gravity (TeVeS) which is a modified gravity theory proposed as an alternative to dark matter to explain the observed gravitational phenomena at galactic and extragalactic scales. TeVeS was developed by Jacob Bekenstein in the early 2000s and is designed to address the dark matter problem by modifying the laws of gravity. Here's an explanation and summary of TeVeS in the context of the dark matter problem. The early 2000s witnessed the development of $f(R)$ gravity, which modified GR by introducing additional functions of the Ricci scalar. Cosmic Acceleration: While $f(R)$ gravity was initially proposed as an alternative to dark matter, it gained attention in explaining cosmic acceleration (dark energy) as well.

Modified gravity theories faced challenges in fully explaining the large-scale structure of the universe and the CMB observations. These constraints, along with dark matter's gravitational effects, continued to play a significant role in cosmological models. In the 2010s, theories like Emergent Gravity (Verlinde's theory) proposed that gravity could emerge from the entanglement of quantum degrees of freedom. These theories suggested that dark matter might be an emergent effect rather than the presence of exotic particles.

The scaling laws for the modifications of the potential functions for MOND suggest that if the relativistic corrections for the relativity model of galactic rotation curves does not accurately fit all geometries and cases of the N body solution, additional dimensions could easily be added to the metric in GR to modify the theory to fit it to each scenario for each scale. But from MOND with the scaling factor this is similar to the zoom operator for my theory of CGR which suggests again the possibility of a 5th variable could be used to modify the 4-d functions so that they can be fitted in virtually any case. Modifying CGR, the Complex valued GR to include the scaling factor

makes it so that the metric as well as the velocities are dependent on the scaling factor or the 5th variable. GR could further be modified to N dimensions, as well as generalizing the mathematical objects in the Einstein-Hilbert Action integral and the Matter Lagrangian for general relativity. The Lagrangians as well as the space-times in some cases will be dependent on the 4-velocity.

If indeed there is real matter there and it is not an affect of matter it still can be possible that the deflection angle becomes such that the light is deflected out of our sight and we physically can not see much of the universe since the light is completely deflected out of the way. This would be in alignment with a complex space time-superluminal theory considering the extremely diffuse density with Snells law where Snells law and optics are known to give Complex solutions. Is that possible that things are much larger than it seems but we can not see it because the light is so distorted? They say it can not be baryonic but if it were superluminal and virtual it could have real energy and a real affect on the visible matter. The electromagnetic fields in many cases give Complex valued solutions as well as the Einstein field equations. What Complex metrics are simple enough for us to work with though and what does this tell us about the virtual particles?

Particle theories

In the paper titled "Colored Dark Matter" authored by Valerio De Luca, Andrea Mitridate, Michele Redi, Juri Smirnov, and Alessandro Strumia [50], the authors explore the intriguing possibility that Dark Matter (DM) is composed of the lightest hadron formed by two stable color octet Dirac fermions (referred to as Q).

It is not clear exactly what is the nature of dark matter if it exists however, at this point, there are still a few dark matter possibilities that are viable. Baryonic matter could still make up the dark matter if it were all tied up in brown dwarfs or in small, dense chunks of heavy elements. These possibilities are known as massive compact halo objects, or MACHOs [51]. But the most common view is that dark matter is not baryonic at all, but that it is made up of other, more exotic particles like axions [52] or WIMPS.

There are multiple candidates responsible for the rotation curve stabilization phenomena exhibited in some galaxies such as Dark Matter which is composed of a fundamentally different particle type and which exists beyond the edge of galaxies. Methods from quantum mechanics such as using the estimated wave functions for the dark matter particles to determine the potential cross section with techniques such as partial wave summation of the dark matter particles. There is much evidence pointing towards the fact that dark matter since it does not interact electromagnetically that it is in fact another form of matter.

Some experiments, like CoGeNT and DAMA/LIBRA [53], appear to show results consistent with the presence of dark matter particles, particularly in the form of annual modulation in event rates. However, other experiments, such as CDMS and XENON100 [54], have reported null results, failing to detect signals that would support the existence of dark matter particles. Some experiments suggest the possibility of dark matter particles, while others do not. This highlights the complexity of the dark matter problem and the need for alternative explanations. This paper will investigate the alternate possibility of dark matter being a relativistic phenomenon and thus the result is that the Newtonian equations which are currently used to compute the rotation curve

forces need modified to accommodate for the relativistic forces. I would like to state here that even if dark matter indeed is an alternate form of matter that we should be able to model it relatively to the visible matter. This is another avenue which could be potentially verified but that is not the topic of this paper.

The search for dark matter particles primarily has been done by looking at the scattering off nucleons such as in the paper: “Implications of CoGeNT’s New Results For Dark Matter Dan Hooper,a,b and Chris Kelsoc” [55]. The CoGeNT collaboration has conducted a significant study involving the analysis of data collected over a span of 15 months. The dataset encompasses the measurement of various characteristics of candidate events associated with nuclear recoils. In particular, they have scrutinized the spectrum of these events and have examined how they vary over time. Remarkably, their findings suggest a remarkable alignment with what would be expected if relatively light dark matter particles were interacting through elastic scattering with atomic nuclei.

Experiments like XENON and LZ [56] use tanks filled with liquid xenon to detect the rare interactions between dark matter particles and xenon nuclei. The detection of scintillation or ionization signals is used to identify dark matter events. Experiments like CDMS and SuperCDMS use cryogenic detectors, often made of germanium or silicon, to search for dark matter interactions through phonon or ionization signals produced when dark matter particles scatter off detector nuclei. The PICO collaboration [57] uses bubble chambers filled with superheated fluid. The passage of a high-energy particle, like a dark matter particle, can trigger the formation of tiny bubbles.

Instruments like the Fermi Gamma-ray Space Telescope [58] and ground-based Cherenkov telescopes [59] like H.E.S.S. and VERITAS [60] look for gamma-ray emissions produced by the annihilation or decay of dark matter particles in regions with high dark matter density, such as the galactic center or dwarf galaxies that orbit the Milky Way and other galaxies. Experiments like AMS-02 [61] on the International Space Station and underground detectors like DAMIC aim to identify cosmic rays produced by dark matter interactions in space or within the Earth.

Particle accelerators like the LHC at CERN aim to produce dark matter particles indirectly by colliding high-energy protons or other particles. Researchers analyze data for unusual or missing energy signatures that could indicate the production of dark matter. Experiments like IceCube [62] in Antarctica use detectors embedded in ice to observe neutrinos. While primarily designed for neutrino astronomy, these detectors can also indirectly probe dark matter interactions, as some dark matter models predict the production of high-energy neutrinos.

Large-scale surveys like the Sloan Digital Sky Survey (SDSS) [63], LSST [64], and Euclid [65] aim to map the distribution of galaxies and galaxy clusters, providing insights into the large-scale structure influenced by dark matter. Experiments located deep underground, such as those in the Sanford Underground Research Facility (SURF) [66] or the Gran Sasso Laboratory [67] in Italy, are shielded from cosmic rays, making them ideal for direct dark matter searches. Indirect detection searches involve looking for secondary particles or radiation produced when WIMPs annihilate or decay in regions of high dark matter density. Instruments like gamma-ray telescopes

e.g., Fermi-LAT [68] and cosmic ray detectors (e.g., AMS-02) are used to observe gamma rays, neutrinos, positrons, or antiprotons produced in WIMP interactions or decays.

Haloscopes [69] are experiments designed to detect axions by converting them into detectable microwave photons in a strong magnetic field. These experiments typically employ high-quality, tunable resonant cavities to enhance the conversion of axions into photons. Sensitive microwave detectors, such as superconducting devices, are used to detect the generated signals. Axion helioscopes aim to detect solar axions produced in the core of the Sun via the Primakoff effect. They focus on converting axions back into X-ray or gamma-ray photons in a strong magnetic field. These experiments utilize large, superconducting magnets, often situated on tracking platforms to follow the Sun's motion. X-ray or gamma-ray detectors are used to capture the reconverted photons. ADMX [70] employs specialized superconducting quantum interference devices (SQUIDs [71]) as detectors, which are highly sensitive to the faint signals resulting from axion-photon conversion.

Thus, we can model both situations, the situation in which the galaxy indeed is balanced by dark matter and one which is described by extra forces we don't know about yet such as relativistic forces. If dark matter is indeed merely a relativistic phenomenon we should still be able to consider the mathematical possibility that such matter can exist mathematically or relatively to the matter in the relativity framework. This is a proposed view such that the virtual matter in the relativity framework relative to the Newtonian framework is needed to describe the wave like behavior known from quantum mechanics for particles and their virtual pair. They may not actually exist but can be used as a tool to describe dynamics of the matter. It is likely that a successful dark matter particle theory in the absence of physical matter will lead to other methods to predict boundaries for other particles.

Not having direct evidence yet when the particle discovery enterprise has been extremely successful to me casts doubt on the existence of a physical dark matter particle but rather the existence of it as a virtual particle and virtual matter. What if we are not using the correct relativistic equations? How much will this throw our numbers off? Could dark matter be our negligence of the angular momenta of each planet moving around each star? Or could the intergalactic medium provide the mass we are missing? Is dark matter in the case of galactic rotation curves actually just external gravitational contributions from galaxies in their local group? What about the possibility that our calculations and estimates for the mass of stars is wrong? It is important to include the masses of all the objects in each solar system not a star? How many massive nonsolar contributors exist in any galactic distribution? Are there large magnetic fields that emanate from the galaxy that could be responsible for the incorrect measurements? Are the stars moving fast enough for relativity to be needed? Is there sufficient gravity from the galaxies within the surrounding clusters and super clusters to affect the Milky Way to be responsible for the rotation curve forces? These are just some questions about the unknowns and uncertainties one might have with regard to the simple model we are creating here. Certainly each of these things can and should be tested. It is very possible that it is a combination of everything combined that makes up for the total difference between observations and theory. It should be stated that even a

new particulate dark matter would be required to be modeled by the relativity theory of gravity. Initial calculations suggest that it is unlikely from large magnetic fields.

So it seems possible that even if dark matter does not exist as a different kind of matter, that we can still obtain a particle model for it to describe its affect on regular matter within the galaxy. This model in which there is physical model then should be equated to the model of relativity with the corrected gravitational potential because this shows how space-time could be used to model other particle interactions such as virtual particles in quantum physics and potentially provide another path to unify quantum mechanics and relativistic classical mechanics. Research suggests, at least half of matter is in between galaxies in the Intergalactic Medium [72]. Some calculations suggest numbers up to 90% on the high end and 50% on the low end for relative amount of mass of the IGM to the Universe. These estimates do not consider dark matter in the calculations but are for ordinary visible matter, mostly hydrogen and helium, the lowest atomic mass atoms. The IGM is not abundantly visible because it is diffuse and in most places transparent.

Because of their brightness, quasar light is used to see scattering in the IGM. As the light from the quasar travels to Earth, some of the light is scattered, absorbed, reflected, and possibly deflected by intervening IGM hydrogen and helium gas. A question which is not the topic of this paper should potentially be explored on a more experimental basis to determine how much the deflection angle would be through the IGM over extremely large distances. The refraction of a beam of light through diffuse hydrogen gas with variable density may not be large but over large distances this may sum to noticeable effects so we should eliminate doubt by putting stronger boundaries on IGM deflection. It seems that refraction is potentially a function of the density gradient if the IGM so that a larger refraction may occur in some places in the universe than others. Is it possible that the refraction of the light through the IGM causes the path variation of the light near clusters since the large scale is big enough? It seems unlikely that the IGM has sufficient mass density to cause gravitational deflection of the quasar light but rather that a small amount of refraction over large distances could be perceived as gravitational deflection.

Owing to the predominant presence of hydrogen atoms in their ground state, the absorption of light within the Intergalactic Medium triggers the Lyman alpha transition. In this process, the electron encircling the hydrogen atom absorbs a photon, transitioning from the ground state ($n=1$) to the first excited state ($n=2$). Termed Lyman alpha absorption [73], this mechanism serves as a pivotal tool for the indirect observation of the IGM. The interaction between photons, particularly those emanating from quasars, and the IGM is scrutinized, allowing for the discernment of the IGM's characteristics.

The luminosity of a quasar illuminates its surroundings, and as the emitted light traverses to Earth, it undergoes absorption by the IGM. This absorption manifests as a distinctive pattern of absorption lines, collectively referred to as the Lyman alpha forest. The Lyman alpha forest, observed in the spectra of quasars, serves as a valuable means to indirectly study the properties and composition of the Intergalactic Medium. This model discussed in the paper is simpler and it is more in alignment of the theory of Gravitational waves since they have been now so readily observed. The existence of the gravitational wave and the mathematical equality of this existence to GEM waves which are essentially uncoupled wave equations it suggests that the space time waves exist with a Gravitoelectric wave perpendicular to a gravitomagnetic wave in the sense that

the gravitomagnetic wave induces the gravitoelectric wave. Really, these are both the same space time but intertwined in such a manner that the one space-time wave which can be represented in the Newtonian approximation as a space-time vector field or the vector field for the gravitational field.

LIGO

LIGO- GW170817 [74], functioning as an interferometer, relies on the detection of its own state changes through a Schwarzschild Transformation within the framework of General Relativity. Specifically, it discerns alterations in its path length induced by the passage of gravitational waves, as predicted by Wheeler in 1955 [75]. The foundational blueprint for constructing the device was derived from this prediction, including the anticipation of 'Space-time Inversion,' also postulated by Wheeler in the same discourse.

In essence, the detection of gravitational waves hinges on the disruption of equilibrium in the orbital dynamics of two source Black Holes, resulting in a distinct signature known as the 'Chirp-Mass.' Consequently, the initial pursuit of 'Space-time Inversion' in the electromagnetic field was deemed less pertinent, as attention should have been directed toward identifying points of spacetime inversion for the gravitoelectric and gravitomagnetic fields.

The inference drawn is that the interaction between different types of gravitational waves and electromagnetic radiation within clusters leads to additional light deflection. This phenomenon can create an illusion of increased galactic mass, emphasizing the interconnectedness of gravitational waves and electromagnetic radiation in shaping our understanding of cosmic structures.

Wheeler's use of syntagm, notably the assertion that "A Gravitational Wave through one viewpoint is Gravitation Without Mass," transcends a mere analogy to a photon without its constituent electron. Instead, he delves into the concept of gravitational waves embodying a form of gravitation devoid of mass, a notion predating the formalization of Information Theory.

Wheeler's insights, though causally rich, surpass the contemporaneous qualitative comprehension of these prescient components. Notably, the collaborative work of Wheeler, Thorne, and Misner in "Gravitation" stands as a foundational reference in the field.

The additional mass discussed arises from the constructive interference of overlapping Gravity Waves emanating from a galaxy in gradual rotation, encompassing approximately half a trillion solar masses. While the Lin-Shu Density Wave [76], expounded in 1962, elucidated the spiral structure and coherence of galaxies, the concept of Gravity Waves had not yet garnered empirical validation, leaving the model in relative obscurity.

Proof of the equivalence of Relativity theory in approximation $v \ll c$ to Gravitodynamics

My original guess based on intuition about dark matter was where beyond a certain velocity, beyond the radius which initially the stabilization velocity occurs at, there was a relativistic effect that caused an electromagnetic energy exchange so that the visible matter beyond the Schwarzschild like radius of the metric for the galaxy would appear black. The idea was that there was indeed visible matter beyond that point but that the theory of relativity modified how we perceive the event. This hypothesis has not been validated since the metric tensor for each of different types of galaxies is not readily known or easily derived in the relativistic context outside

of linearization of the equations which is what is discussed here. It should be stated that this hypothesis is not necessarily ruled out because there may be some frame that this can be selected to be true. It seems that this potentially could be used to show the relationship between the fields and the particle definitions for dark matter as defined from a transformation of the definitions of the visible matter when it passes the Schwarzschild boundary. This must be proven by first establishing the metric tensors as well as the density profiles and the fields for each of the different types of galaxies and seeing if the calculations from the relativistic metric match the second Schwarzschild radius for the galaxy.

Using the spherical coordinates, all masses have a Schwarzschild radius. Using the Schwarzschild equation the radius I obtain for the Milky Way is: $r_s = 8.9 * 10^{15}m$. this suggests that the schwarzschild radius would occur within the radius of the milky way. This is the solution for the Schwarzschild equation which is essentially correctly the event horizon of the black hole.

The linearization of the Einstein field equations [77] is equivalent to analyzing the Einstein Equations in the Newtonian Limit. It turns out that this has been done in a few different ways, in textbooks and in papers and is common practice. Apparently the linearized equations of GR, or the equations of GR in the Newtonian Limit are almost equal to those for Gravitodynamics but does imply that there is a gravitodynamic effect. This effect would be supported by the observation of gravitational waves since gravitodynamics predicts gravitational waves as well. This is not surprising at all since the mathematical structure of the theory of electrodynamics which with the correct mathematical tools can essentially be derived from the Gauss' law for electrodynamics. Modern electrodynamics can be written in the form of Maxwell's equations as well as the Lienard Wiechert equations for the fields. The idea is that as the charge moves there exists a field that corresponds to said motion. The Electric field from Maxwell's laws induce a Magnetic field. Together both fields can be written as a single entity in the form of the electromagnetic field tensor. More generally in a case where we consider two charges or the two body problem for electrodynamics, the main and essential difference between gravitodynamics and electrodynamics is that the charge if replaced with m must be the absolute value of the charge so that only can there be positive value mass within the gravitational equivalent to the Maxwell equations.

This occurs in many classical texts on general relativity but the best one that I have recently found is from Wald general relativity [78]. It shows how in the weak field limit which is essentially the same thing as $v \ll c$ then, solving problem 3 of Wald, referencing the solution I found on the forum then we can essentially solve this section. The following solution to problem 3 is not my own solution and I found this essentially within the contexts of Wald's textbook and discussions on Physics forums between users.

From General Relativity, Wald problem 3 is written as: "If we assume that the time derivatives of $\bar{h}_{ab}$ are negligible, then the space-space components of $\bar{h}_{ab}$ vanish, and we find that to linear order in the velocity of the test body, the geodesic equation now yields:

$$\vec{a} = -\vec{E} - 4\vec{v}x\vec{B} \tag{Eq 1}$$

Where $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ are defined in terms of A_a by the same formulas as in electromagnetism,"

Advancing to demonstrate that linearized gravity predicts gravitational effects akin to electromagnetism resulting from the motion of masses. Specifically, within the linear order concerning the velocity of a test body, the geodesic equation furnishes an analogue of the Lorentz Force equation. Summarizing the pertinent Newtonian limit section as outlined on page 74 of Wald: Under the weak field limit, this implies that the metric is expressed as:

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} + h_{\mu\nu} \quad \text{Eq 2)}$$

$\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the flat space-time metric from special relativity and $h_{\mu\nu}$ is a small perturbation of this metric. The weak field limit, synonymous with "linearized gravity," involves retaining only terms of linear order in $h_{\mu\nu}$ for computations, assuming the negligible impact of higher-order terms. The covariant derivative, symbolically represented as ∇_μ , can be approximated as ∂_μ in our first-order calculations when applied to $h_{\mu\nu}$ or an expression involving $h_{\mu\nu}$. This substitution is permissible as the Christoffel symbol terms will not exhibit first-order dependence on $h_{\mu\nu}$. In the weak field limit, the Christoffel symbols can be expressed in terms of the small perturbation, with $\nabla_\mu \eta_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu \eta_{\mu\nu} = 0$

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\alpha = \frac{1}{2} \eta^{\alpha\beta} (\partial_\mu h_{\nu\beta} + \partial_\nu h_{\mu\beta} - \partial_\beta h_{\mu\nu}) \quad \text{Eq 3)}$$

Defining the following metric in terms of the perturbation metric makes the math simpler:

$$\bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = h_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} \eta_{\mu\nu} h \quad \text{Eq 4)}$$

Defining h conventionally as h_μ^μ . Taking the trace of both sides of **Eq 4)** results in:

$$\bar{h}_\mu^\mu = h_\mu^\mu - \frac{1}{2} \eta_\mu^\mu h \quad \text{Eq 5)}$$

Direct substitution of the definition of h_μ^μ gives:

$$\bar{h} = h - \frac{1}{2} (4)h = -h \quad \text{Eq 6)}$$

Inserting **Eq 6)** back into **Eq 4)** gives

$$h_{\mu\nu} = \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} \eta_{\mu\nu} \bar{h}. \quad \text{Eq 7)}$$

In the Lorentz Gauge, the Einstein Equations undergo simplification. Given the gauge freedom inherent in linearized gravity (additional details available on page 75 in Wald), a gauge transformation can be employed to streamline the Einstein equations to:

$$\partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} = -16\pi T_{\mu\nu} \quad \text{Eq 8)}$$

Considering the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ presume that only lower-order effects of motion are considered, and stresses are neglected. The stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ can then be approximated to linear order in velocity t_μ by:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = 2t_\mu J_\nu - \rho t_\mu t_\nu \quad \text{Eq 9)}$$

In the equation $J_\nu = -T_{\mu\nu}t^\mu$ represents the 4-vector mass current density. Assuming coordinates and considering small velocities, we can approximate the velocity four-vector as $t^\mu = (1,0,0,0)$. Therefore, in matrix form, the stress-energy tensor is expressed as:

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho & p_x & p_y & p_z \\ p_x & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_y & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_z & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 10)}$$

In this context, where $\vec{p} = (p_x, p_y, p_z)$ represents momentum, the subsequent step involves establishing the counterpart of Maxwell's equations. Focusing on the time-time and space-time components of Einstein's equation yields:

$$\partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha \bar{h}_\mu = -16\pi J_\mu \quad \text{Eq 11)}$$

Contrasting with the first equation of Maxwell's Electromagnetism in a flat 4-dimensional space-time,

$$\partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha A_\nu = -4\pi J_\nu, \quad \text{Eq 12)}$$

The gravitomagnetic vector potential can be defined from

$$A_\alpha = -\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu, \quad \text{Eq 13)}$$

For velocities that are small relative to the speed of light, $t^\nu = (1,0,0,0)$

$$A_\nu = -\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu 0} \quad \text{Eq 14)}$$

Using **Eq 14**) the analog of $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ in terms of $A_\nu = (-\phi, \vec{A})$:

$$\vec{E} = -\vec{\nabla}\phi - \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} \quad \text{Eq 15)}$$

$$\vec{B} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A} \quad \text{Eq 16)}$$

Now, proceeding with addressing problem 3 in Wald, wherein the trajectory of the test body is determined by the geodesic equation,

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\mu \frac{dx^\rho}{d\tau} \frac{dx^\sigma}{d\tau} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 17)}$$

The world line of the particle in global inertial coordinates is denoted as $x^\mu(\tau)$. Assuming that the motion of the test body is significantly slower than the speed of light, proper time τ can be approximated by the coordinate time t . Thus, we can express:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{dt^2} + \Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\mu \frac{dx^\rho}{dt} \frac{dx^\sigma}{dt} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 18)}$$

Defining $\frac{dx^\rho}{dt} = v^\rho$ and moving the second term of **Eq 18**) to the RHS, this yields:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{dt^2} = -\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\mu v^\rho v^\sigma \quad \text{Eq 19)}$$

Changing μ to i , where $i = 1,2,3$ and defining $a^i = -\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^i v^\rho v^\sigma$. Even though i only runs along the spatial indicies 1 to 3, ρ and σ range from 0 to 3. Approximating the derivatives as 0, the nonzero Christoffel Symbols can now be calculated. From **Eq 3**,

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_{00}^\alpha &= \frac{1}{2}\eta^{\alpha\beta}(-\partial_\beta h_{00}) \\ &= \partial^\beta h_{00}\end{aligned}\tag{Eq 20}$$

From **Eq 7**) and **Eq 14**) and recalling that $A_0 = -\phi$:

$$\begin{aligned}h_{00} &= \bar{h}_{00} - \frac{1}{2}\eta_{00}\bar{h} \\ &= -4A_0 + \frac{1}{2}(4A_0) \\ &= 4\phi - 2\phi \\ &= 2\phi\end{aligned}$$

So, the Christoffel symbols can be expressed in terms of the potential:

$$\Gamma_{00}^\beta = -\partial^\beta \phi\tag{Eq 21}$$

Using **Eq 3**) and again **Eq 14**) the Christoffel symbols become

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_{0\beta}^\alpha &= \Gamma_{\beta 0}^\alpha = \frac{1}{2}\eta^{\alpha k}(\partial_\beta h_{0k} - \partial_k h_{0\beta}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\beta h_0^\alpha - \partial^\alpha h_{0\beta}) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(-4)(\partial_\beta A^\alpha - \partial^\alpha A_\beta) \\ \Gamma_{\beta 0}^\alpha &= 2(\partial^\alpha A_\beta - \partial_\beta A^\alpha)\end{aligned}\tag{Eq 22}$$

The electromagnetic field tensor is defined as: $F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu h_\nu - \partial_\nu h_\mu$. Inserting this into **Eq 22**) gives:

$$\Gamma_{0\beta}^\alpha = \Gamma_{\beta 0}^\alpha = 2F_\beta^\alpha\tag{Eq 23}$$

Since $\frac{dx^\alpha}{dt} = v^\alpha$ this means $v^0 = 1$. Therefore, plugging in the results from **Eq 21**) and **Eq 22**) into **Eq 19**) produces an expression for the acceleration in terms of the gravitational potential and the electromagnetic field tensor:

$$\begin{aligned}a^\alpha &= -\Gamma_{\rho\sigma}^\alpha v^\rho v^\sigma \\ a^\alpha &= -\Gamma_{00}^\alpha - \Gamma_{0\beta}^\alpha v^\beta - \Gamma_{\beta 0}^\alpha v^\beta\end{aligned}\tag{Eq 24}$$

Which implies

$$a^\alpha = -\partial^\alpha \phi - 4F_\beta^\alpha v^\beta \quad \text{Eq 25)}$$

Writing **Eq 21)** and **Eq 23)** in index notation and approximating $\frac{\partial A_\mu}{\partial t} = B^0$ **Eq 16)**, the gravitomagnetic and gravitoelectric fields can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} E^\alpha &= -\partial^\alpha \phi \\ B^\alpha &= \epsilon^{\alpha\beta k} \partial_\beta A_k \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 26)}$$

Where $\epsilon^{\alpha\beta k}$ is the fully antisymmetric Levi Civita symbol detailed on pages 432 and 433 of wald but also texts on classical mechanics such as Taylor. Lastly, we write $\vec{v}x\vec{B}$ in index notation and find:

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{v}x\vec{B})_\alpha &= \epsilon_{\alpha\beta k} v^\beta B^k \\ &= \epsilon_{\alpha\beta k} v^\beta \epsilon^{klm} \partial_l A_m \\ &= (\epsilon^{klm} \epsilon_{k\alpha\beta}) v^\beta \partial_l A_m \\ &= (\delta_\alpha^l \delta_\beta^m v^\beta - \delta_\alpha^m \delta_\beta^l v^\beta) \partial_l A_m \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 27)}$$

$$(\vec{v}x\vec{B})_\alpha = v^m \partial_\alpha A_m - v^l \partial_l A_\alpha \quad \text{Eq 28)}$$

Using the electromagnetic field tensor **Eq 27)** becomes:

$$(\vec{v}x\vec{B})_\alpha = F_{\alpha\beta} v^\beta \quad \text{Eq 29)}$$

Eq 25) becomes **Eq 1)** with the insertion of the definitions from **Eq 29)** and **Eq 26)**.

We see that in general that the gravitomagnetic field in the linearized case can be expressed as a function of the space-time metric $\bar{h}_{\mu\nu}$. As well as all the Maxwell equations can be expressed in terms of the metric for space time:

$$\vec{B} = -\vec{\nabla}x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \quad \text{Eq 30)}$$

$$E^\mu = \partial^\mu A_\nu = -\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \quad \text{Eq 31)}$$

With

$$\partial^\mu = \left(\begin{array}{c} \vec{\nabla} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \end{array} \right) \quad \text{Eq 32)}$$

Then by applying Maxwell's law:

$$\vec{\nabla}x\vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad \text{Eq 33)}$$

The faraday law can be expressed in terms of space-time:

$$\vec{\nabla}x\vec{E} = -\vec{\nabla}x \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 34)}$$

As well as:

Eq 35)

$$-\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right)$$

To give our linear laws for the space-time metric differential equations:

Eq 36)

$$-\vec{\nabla} x \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right)$$

Summarizing the Maxwell differential equations for the space-time:

Table 1

Maxwells Equations Space-time differential form	Name of Laws
$-\vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}$	Gauss' Law (Electric)
$-\vec{\nabla} x \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right)$	Faraday-Lenz
$-\vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) = 0$	Gauss' Law (Magnetic)
$\vec{\nabla} x \left(\left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \right)$ $= \mu_0 \vec{J} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right)}{\partial t}$	Ampere-Maxwell

Table 2

	ME's In Integral Form	Name of Laws
1	$-\oiint \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \cdot da = \frac{M_{enclosed}}{\epsilon_{0g}}$	Gauss' Law (Electric)
2	$-\oint \left(\partial^\mu \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \cdot dl$ $= -\frac{d}{dt} (GravitoMag. Flux)$	Faraday-Lenz
3	$-\oiint \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \cdot da = 0$	Gauss' Law (Magnetic)
4	$-\oint \left(\vec{\nabla} x \left(\frac{1}{4} \bar{h}_{\mu\nu} t^\nu \right) \right) \cdot dl$ $= \mu_{0g} I_{enclosed}$ $+ \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{d}{dt} (Elect. Flux) \right)$	Ampere-Maxwell

Of course the Maxwell equations for the space time depend on the gauge selections as well as the fact that we are considering linearized spaces relatively to the original differential equations. The application the operation of linearization of Einstein's equations produces Maxwell equations so a good theorem about deriving other types of Maxwell equations might come from different degrees of analysis. For example the quadratization of the Einstein's equations would give a second order approximation of the Einstein equations which would produce Maxwell type equations that have more terms and are in the second degree. This could be done theoretically for nth degree Maxwell equations where theoretically in the general definition of space time it may be possible that the Einstein equations contain solutions of infinite degree. What are the maxwell-einstein equations for the property color? What is the space-time metric relation to the color force? The complex Maxwell equations can be obtained for the Newtonian limit by considering complex metrics and potentially, complex velocities.

The circular motion seen by the stars in the galaxy, the velocity tangent to the circle and the acceleration towards the center of the circle, by the right hand rule the direction of the magnetic field is in the downward direction, orthogonal to the acceleration, velocity and magnetic field. The direction of the acceleration is in the opposite direction of the gravitoelectric field and the gravitoelectric field is orthogonal to the gravitomagnetic field. Placing B in the downward direction so that the analog between electromagnetism can be made in the case of galactic rotation curves, and assuming that this force is responsible for the effect the acceleration equation would have the positive radial force that would correspond to the direction of the dark matter force. From the Biot-Savart law, the gravitomagnetic field for the matter current in the outer edges of the rotation curves of the galaxy is a function of the radius.

By analogy to the case where we look at the planets as electrons in the framework which are revolving around a galactic nucleus, a magnetic field is generated by the motion of the electrons around the proton. Considering a proton orbiting the electron as a circular loop of current, which generates a magnetic field according to the formula:

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 I}{2r}. \quad \text{Eq 37)}$$

The current I is $\frac{dm}{dt}$ where m is the nucleus' mass Nm and t is the period of oscillation $\frac{2\pi r}{v}$ (v the velocity), which gives and effective magnetic field strength:

$$B = \frac{\mu_{0g} Nm v}{4\pi r^2} = \frac{1}{c^2 \epsilon_{g0}} \left(\frac{Nm v}{4\pi r^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 38)}$$

The gauge transformation theory and the applications used for linearization from Lorentz gauge should be generalized to consider the other families of differential equations. Other approximations are known in literature shows how to reduce Einstein's equations to the Newtonian equations like coulomb law.

The complex valued field equations for general relativity can be derived in N-d from Lagrangian variation. It might be possible to apply weak field limit to show dark particle relative to real particle which in one framework is a field effect but in another framework is a particle.

Due to the fact that Poisson's equation, a differential equation which is a modification of the differential equation which describes electromagnetic phenomena, it must be that a better understanding of the frequency analysis will likely produce methodology to describe solutions of other similar differential equations.

Inserting values of velocity $v = V + c$, where c is the speed of light into the Lorentz Transformation, the variables become imaginary. It is this simple fact which will persist in every field theory because of the fact that the transformation factor is defined as a function to a half power, and so ultimately the definition for values larger than the speed of light, mathematically speaking with respect to relativistic transformations, are complex. After investigating electrodynamics looking for places where complex numbers appear in the solution method or definition, one finds that although the definitions are different, they are consistent with the theories defined over the real domain.

This can be done by using the Lienard wiechert potential representation of the G field and Lorentz force equations to show how an extra force term is present relative to the purely Newtonian circular motion representation with Newtonian force. By setting the frameworks equal by adding the Newtonian equivalent to the gravitodynamic case it can be seen that the gravitational energy of the gravitodynamic case of the stellar mass is less than the energy in the Newtonian case because in the gravitodynamic case the mass appears to be less massive as compared to the Newtonian mass as a result of relativity of the motion of the star. So there is a breaking of symmetry between the frameworks. The framework chosen is what the answer will be described in terms of. If the Newtonian framework is used then relative to the correct gravitodynamic framework in this case using another equivalent situation which is modeled with circular orbits that would produce the equivalent force effect is binary rotation in the gravitational case. The main issue is that the Newtonian equations do not have the geometry baked into them like the theory of relativity. We can for example use the same mass, and the same stellar orbit on the same star but describe it instead as a single 2 body keplerian circular solution as a binary star system which has the same force. Dividing by two, the trajectory of the circular motion of the star can be represented as a sum of the 2 body keplerian solution and the binary star system solution where the difference in kinetic energy between Newtonian representation 1 of the circular motion and Newtonian representation 2 of the circular motion and setting that equal to the force term, it shows how the force can create the illusion of the single stellar mass being pulled by a virtual dark particle. The virtual dark particle would be essentially a binary pair with inverted coordinates so that the energy of the dark-visible pair of particles matches the energy of the observations. It might be possible to show with complex valued relativity that the dark particle is a field effect particle and is a virtual particle that is created from the force.

The absorption of a dark photon has the same effect as the absorption of a photon since the dark particle exists as a binary pair to every single mass representation. This is a result of the Unified Field Theory and the conservation of energy. So my modeling masses as point masses at the smallest scale it can be shown that they need another dark particle or virtual pair that balances them.

The photon is a virtual particle that has a real and imaginary part so that's why the photon would theoretically be the same as the dark photon. This would be expected because directional swap of the gravitational field for Unified Field Theory representation of the particle becomes

inward if the mass were negative. Such a negative mass is required if the dark particle is to be modeled relatively to the UFT model of the particle. The usual notion of mass and relativistic mass depicts the connectedness of the definition of mass and the relative motion of mass. So as the velocity of the object is relativistic, the mass can become contracted and as a result the energy becomes contracted. This perspective has always been confusing to me as well as not mathematically rigorous enough. Often I think of the mass as being an invariant, unchanging number, but the velocity is a function of time. So as time goes on, the energy which is by definition a function of the mass and velocity, therefore is a function of time. The time dependence of the energy term comes from the time dependence on the velocity function. So as the coordinates are transformed the velocity function is transformed and therefore the energy is transformed. In this perspective, negative mass can be interpreted essentially as a result of imaginary valued velocities. Antiparticles then have negative time since they have a negative frequency. Virtual particles of the type with imaginary time then will have imaginary velocities and negative energy. AntiVirtual particles theoretically then would just be the opposite of the virtual particles and move in negative imaginary time.

If there was no access to light but you knew that you were accelerating on a circular path you could model the path infinitely many ways to construct the correct answer such as is done in quantum mechanics by defining the best answer as a sum of all possible answers but this would not tell you about the inner workings of the fields.

Hypothesis: The Newtonian force term corrections are given by:

$$dF = dm * (v \times \vec{B}_G) \tag{Eq 39)}$$

Where B_G is the gravitomagnetic field from the universes expansion. It is a small constant but when large forces are integrated over this force is non-negligible. When this term is relativistic there will be other corrections needed.

In the weak field case as represented by gravitodynamics would have gravitational waves which are by definition gravitomagnetic waves. Interestingly there is a connection between the wave equation Laplace's differential equation and Poisson's differential equation because of course the Laplace equation is the homogenous version of Poisson's equation.. By transformation of variables the wave equation becomes the Laplace differential equation. This is what led me to investigate the Riemann-Cauchy conditions in Complex analysis with operator theory [79]. I think this is in general because there is a connection between the Harmonic Gauge and the Lorentz Gauge. Essentially the choice of gauge is related to the definition of the small perturbation metric. Then following similar procedures and assumptions the wave equation can be derived from the linearization of the Einstein field equations.

Following the results of my unified field theory, the usual theory of relativity can be extended to N dimensions such that the metric of galaxies have another dimension so the complex coordinates can be calculated.

The Unified Field Theory after first development appeared to be a completely alternate theory of Relativity with additional terms and dimensions we have not accounted for with a form of hidden variables. Firstly, the unified field theory was without knowledge of Einstein suggesting

that the metric tensor must be complex in his later years working on a unified field theory essentially a Complex extension of General Relativity designed to handle the complex coordinates obtained for superluminal velocities in the standard theory of special relativity. By studying the mathematical effects of superluminal velocities on the Lorentz equations it can be seen how the equations become modified. The usefulness of such a modification is that it gives insight as to how the mathematical model for the complex coordinate systems should be developed since essentially these equations are derived from considering a pulse of light moving along the Imaginary axis.

The theory I independently developed I called “the Complex Numbered Theory of General Relativity,” and in my YouTube videos I have begun the initial lectures on this extension of Relativity. After graduating I had obtained evidence that there already was alternate Complex Space-time theories to extend relativity. There are many similarities between those theories and my theory but my theory by definition simply is the rederivation of the regular equations of relativity with the singular modification that the coordinates take the form: $x_\mu = u_\mu + iv_\mu$ and the resulting required constraints for the regular real terms of the theory to be derived. Another major feature of the theory of CGR was that of the Zoom operator. The zoom operator is an operator that transforms the coordinates so that the observer at our scale can imagine the quantum phenomena. After looking at the partial differential equations obtained it became clear after a long time that the effect of the zoom operator was having on the equations was that it was essentially like having another dimension.

The unified field theory requires the complex space-time tensors from the Complex Numbered theory of general relativity I found through independent means, but as it happens, as it usually happens when researching things, what appeared and felt like a discovery was indeed a discovery relative to me but in his later years I found whole articles written by Einstein about unified field theory and the complex coordinate requirement as well as whole books devoted to complex space times complex theories of relativity and complex differential equations. Nonetheless for the unified field theory the mathematical objects including the coordinates need modified so that the mathematical objects can contain the information in quantum field theory. By using nested matrices the mathematical objects of the complex numbered theory of general relativity can be defined. Then arbitrarily the unified field theory becomes defined as general operators acting on the general mathematical objects which correspond to each type of particle and physical object that can be modeled. The matrices provide the relationship to group theory with representation theory. The last part of the unified field theory after being able to define the structure of the fields for each particle and the particle structure is the probabilistic relationship to the complex space-times so that the statistics of quantum mechanics can be used to derive the relationships.

As a result of this work, it suggests that there are other representations of any such unified field theory and that some aspects of physics that have conflicts are potential areas for discovery since the collective picture of reality no matter what theory we use gives observational data for which any such theory should match. The string theory as well as the Lagrangian's for other theories such as the M theory should fall under the unified field theory model. The UFT in short

modifies the kernel of the Action integral to more general mathematical objects to produce more general spaces.

In the most general form we can consider the matrix set of Einstein field equations for each of the n stars within each of the k galaxies as:

$$R_{\mu\nu}^{nk} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}^{nk} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^{nk} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}^{nk} \quad \text{Eq 40)}$$

$$\frac{d^2x^{nk\mu}}{ds^2} + \Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} \left(\frac{dx^{nk\alpha}}{ds} \right) \left(\frac{dx^{nk\beta}}{ds} \right) = 0$$

In general, however, it must be true that n is a function of the enclosed volume. And it would be implied that if in the far removed case where there is non-interaction between the two galaxies we can integrate over the areas to produce the total number N within the area A and the resulting Total Energy tensor. Integrating over n essentially makes these equations become a single equation for the galaxy with a single density profile.

In principle, the nested matrices which are matrices which each have Einstein field equations would reduce the n systems of EFE's to a single system of equations:

$$\iint dn \left(R_{\mu\nu}^{n(k=1)} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}^{n(k=1)} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^{n(k=1)} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}^{n(k=1)} \right) \quad \text{Eq 42)}$$

$$\rightarrow \left(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \right)$$

So the singular set of equations can be used to describe the Einstein field equations because the n masses become mass density when integrating over each dn . This is why the components of the stress energy field tensor components is density functions and current functions. In the interaction case there are cross terms that must be added and are far more complex than the regular simple Einstein field equations.

But in the case of the single galaxy with $k = 1$, and the case with 2 galaxies with $k = 2$ interacting galaxies, the equations can be summarized in this form and realistically it is a matter of asking for how many interactions have you modeled and solved for and cases for which exact data was used to fit for the n stars.

In general for k systems each containing n bodies:

$$\iint dn^k \left(R_{\mu\nu}^{nk} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}^{nk} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^{nk} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}^{nk} \right) \rightarrow \left(R_{\mu\nu}^k - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}^k + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^k = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}^k \right) \quad \text{Eq 43)}$$

If you want to include the total reality, the tensor expands where you consider the number of planets p for each star, then you can add another parameter to make the Einstein field equations become:

$$R_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} \quad \text{Eq 44)}$$

Also:

$$\iint dn^{kp} \left(R_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}^{nkp} \right) \rightarrow \left(R_{\mu\nu}^k - \frac{1}{2} R g_{\mu\nu}^k + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu}^k = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}^k \right) \quad \text{Eq 45)}$$

Then we can make assumptions about the area integration within small regions as we take smaller and smaller integrals. If the milky way has $k = 1$ and Andromeda has $k = 2$, a similar question arises when trying to model the interaction of two hurricane systems when looking at the planets as the same scaling as molecules. It is fair to evaluate for each k over all matter and then represent both systems essentially as two objects that have gravity.

Then, using the shape mass and density profiles the gravitational vector field for the far away objects can be modeled in approximation. If the other galaxy $k = 2$ moves close enough then the details become important where the positions of the stars at that point in time and the more data you have the better its going to be at simulating the galaxy interaction. This is a true N body problems where there are cross terms and it is expected that the computational time will be extremely high for detailed results.

Classical/Newtonian Mechanics and Gravitodynamics For 2 body and N body Systems and N-K body Dynamic Systems

Refer to chapter 4 by Taylor Classical Mechanics [80] for a fuller description of the information summarized here. Firstly Lagrangians in classical mechanics can be defined as the difference between the kinetic and potential energy. The potential energy in a 2 body system composed of two masses would be:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) = -\frac{Gm_1m_2}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|} \quad \text{Eq 46)}$$

And the lagrangian is in the gravitostatic case:

$$L = \sum_{k=1}^2 \frac{1}{2} m r_k^{\dot{}}^2 - \phi(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) \quad \text{Eq 47)}$$

The Hamilton action principle acts on the Action integral which essentially is an integral of the Lagrangian of the system:

$$S = \int L dt \quad \text{Eq 48)}$$

Where S is the action integral must be stationary. This condition implies the existence of the Euler-Lagrange Equations and this belongs to the subject of the Calculus of Variations. In field theory this principle is known as variation. Variation of the action integral derives the Euler-Lagrange equations. The gravitational field is a vector field defined by the gradient of the Potential function in gravitostatics:

$$F = -\nabla\phi \quad \text{Eq 49)}$$

The lagrangian for the electromagnetic field theory can be written as in classical form:

$$L = T - (m\phi - \dot{\mathbf{r}}\mathbf{A}) \quad \text{Eq 50)}$$

This can also be written in the 4d tensor form using the electromagnetic field tensor. as well and it should be noted that in the weak field case there would be an equivalent gravitational field tensor to that of the electromagnetic field tensor. Here A is the gravitomagnetic vector potential. The angular momentum for the two body system is:

$$l = \mathbf{r}_1 \times \mathbf{p}_1 + \mathbf{r}_2 \times \mathbf{p}_2 \quad \text{Eq 51)}$$

Using polar coordinates with r and θ in terms of which the lagrangian becomes:

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \mu (\dot{r}^2 + r^2 \dot{\theta}^2) - \phi(r) - \dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{A} \quad \text{Eq 52)}$$

Since the lagrangian is not a function of the angle, it is ignorable and the Lagrange equation corresponding to ϕ is just:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\phi}} = \mu r^2 \dot{\phi} = \text{constant} = l \quad \text{Eq 53)}$$

This equation essentially is just a statement of the conservation of momentum. Transform Lagrangian and Euler-lagrange equations to spherical coordinates and the radial equation can be defined as:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial r} = \frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{r}} \quad \text{Eq 54)}$$

Which is:

$$\mu r \dot{\phi}^2 - \frac{dU}{dr} = \mu \ddot{r} \quad \text{Eq 55)}$$

Where μ is the reduced mass. The fictitious centrifugal force is:

$$F_{cf} = \mu r \dot{\phi}^2 = \frac{l^2}{\mu r^3} \quad \text{Eq 56)}$$

The centrifugal potential energy is defined as:

$$\phi_{cf}(r) = \frac{l^2}{2\mu r^2} \quad \text{Eq 57)}$$

And the effective potential energy, $\phi_{eff}(r) = \phi(r) + \phi_{cf}(r)$

The Equation of the orbit can be determined by writing the radial equation in terms of forces with

$$F = -\frac{d\phi}{dr}$$

$$\mu \ddot{r} = F(r) + \frac{l^2}{\mu r^3} \quad \text{Eq 58)}$$

To write the equation in terms of ϕ , make the variable transformation: $u = \frac{1}{r}$. Using this method we obtain a centrifugal term which would act as a force on the stars in the same direction as dark matter force term. The centrifugal force has an associated centrifugal potential energy. This term doesn't seem to matter as much for large r since the proportion to r^{-2} . This essentially gives us the differential equations we can solve.

The orbit equation can be obtained by solving the Kepler differential equation and it's the equation can give the equation of a hyperbola, ellipse, circle and parabola. The equation of GR particle dynamics in a spherical symmetric geometry apparently given by Einstein was:

$$\left(\frac{dx}{d\theta}\right)^2 = \frac{2A}{B^2} + \frac{\alpha}{B^2}x - x^2 + \alpha x^3$$

Where $x = \frac{1}{r}$ is the inverted radius; A and B are the total energy and angular momentum, and $\alpha = 2r_s$ where r_s is the Schwarzschild radius. If the galactic center is not moving then we can use the equation. This leads to a particle moving in a one-dimensional effective potential:

$$\Phi(r) = -\frac{GMm}{r} + \frac{L^2}{2\mu r^2} - \frac{G(M+m)L^2}{c^2\mu r^3} \quad \text{Eq 59)}$$

Apparently the first two terms are well-known classical energies, the first being the attractive Newtonian gravitational potential energy and the second corresponding to the repulsive centrifugal potential energy; however, the third terms is an attractive term unique to general relativity. This effect would also be able to be seen in the 2 body electromagnetic problem. And since there is a direct analog with gravitoelectromagnetic equations, it is expected that this extra term here is from the “gravitomagnetic” part of space-time in the Newtonian sense. Circular orbits and their stability in keplerian solution: Circular orbits occur when the force is zero:

$$F(r) = -\frac{dV}{dr} = 0 = -\frac{mc^2}{2r^4}(r_s r^2 - 2a^2 r + 3r_s a^2) \quad \text{Eq 60)}$$

Namely, when the opposing forces of Newtonian gravity and the distinctive attraction associated with general relativity precisely counterbalance the repulsive centrifugal force. This equilibrium is achievable at two specific radii, designated herein as r_{inner} and r_{outer} :

$$r_{inner} = \frac{a^2}{r_s} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{3r_s^2}{a^2}} \right) = \frac{3a^2}{r_{outer}} \quad \text{Eq 61)}$$

$$r_{outer} = \frac{a^2}{r_s} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{3r_s^2}{a^2}} \right)$$

These values are derived using the quadratic formula. The inclusion of the third term is necessary due to the presence of precession, a measurable phenomenon associated with a precession force acting on celestial bodies, as seen in the two-body case of Mercury. In the realm of general relativity, this manifests as the perihelion shift. Here, L represents the semi-major axis, T is the orbital period, c is the speed of light, and e is the orbital eccentricity, offering a solution to the two-body problem within the framework of general relativity. The orbital precession rate can be determined through the utilization of the radial effective potential ϕ . When there is a small radial deviation from a circular orbit of radius r_{outer} , it will undergo stable oscillations with a specific angular frequency. Omitting the derivation, the precession angle can be expressed as:

$$\sigma = \frac{24\pi^3 L^2}{T^2 c^2 (1 - e^2)} \quad \text{Eq 62)}$$

One of the major initial tests of GR was the accurate calculation of the precession rate. As a side note: if the equations do not match observations we should consider higher order terms for the potential function as well as adding the gravitomagnetic term. So it should be understood that due to relativity not only is there another term from gravitomagnetism but the potential function will be modified too and result is that there may be precession. Now, if every star has a precession angle then one can imagine how for each star there is a precession force that adds up to a large precession force on the galaxy itself.

Apparently research has already been done on the strength of gravitomagnetic fields from spinning masses. The gravitomagnetic field at the equator is:

$$\vec{B}_g = \left(\frac{G}{5c^2}\right)\left(\frac{m}{r}\right)\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}\right) = \frac{2\pi r g}{5c^2 T} \quad \text{Eq 63)}$$

From this calculation it follows that earth's equatorial gravitomagnetic field is about $3.12 * 10^{-7} \text{ g/c}$. Such a field is extremely weak, and again the Gravity Probe B set out to acquire the data. I guess this is because there is a time dependence in the change of mass for the gravitational mass current in the GEM equations. By the hypothesis, in some case, we would expect that there is an equivalent form to the gravitational case:

$$F = GM\vec{E}_g + GM(V \times \vec{B}_g) \quad \text{Eq 64)}$$

And since there is circular motion $F = 0$, and

$$(V \times \vec{B}_g) = -\vec{E}_g$$

Such that the balancing effect which allows circular motion is because:

$$GM(V \times \vec{B}_g) = \text{Dark Matter Force} \quad \text{Eq 65)}$$

This component is essentially from the angular momentum of the galaxy. Lienard Wiechert potentials show how with Lorentz force law the total force exists for the case of electric charge but with GEM relation it can be seen as well that gravity would have the same expected effects. After this is done for the Newtonian case, clearly the relativity formulation can be built from the Newtonian approximations for simple galaxies.

The reason we can define the mass of the galaxy by adding all the stars is because each star can be viewed as a dm with an average mass. The density integral is really just an approximation of a sum such as the Riemann sum:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \rho(x_i) \Delta x = \int_0^b \rho(x) dx \quad \text{Eq 66)}$$

This is the same thing as the matter current and the gravitomagnetic field is a function of the matter current:

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = \frac{d\rho}{dt} V + \rho \frac{dV}{dt} \quad \text{Eq 67)}$$

Thus, the extra force implies the extra term presence of mass density. That part of the function can probably just be carried through all of these things.

The density on a technicality is a function of volume. This is the same with stars as well and this is because of zoom. If you look at the layers inside the earth, all in the immediate vicinity, the density function is the same but as you zoom out over multiple layers, the density of the layers changes. So the density is a function of r, but if r is a 3d function then indeed density is a function of Volume. Maybe we should also be considering the time derivative of the density functions to get the 4d picture since this isn't simply some static density function.

Hypothesis: The sum of the masses from galactic rotation curves that is missing in a cluster is equivalent to the missing mass from lensing.

Testing this hypothesis: Testing this hypothesis can be done by summing the missing mass from all the major contributors in a cluster and comparing the mass estimates from gravitational lensing.

Error Functions and Stability: error function method for each galaxy, using error function data to plot gravitomagnetic and gravitational field. Use error functions to fit the theory to observation.

Is the method used for measuring velocity data relative to us, simply from the observations or is it accommodating for the fact that we are moving and that our observations must be transformed to understand the phenomena? Is it possible that we must transform even the gravitational lensing equations as well?

Surface brightness profiles approximately correspond to the density because the brighter areas mean that there must be more stars there and if there are more stars there must be more mass there and therefore the density is higher where it is brighter. In the Newtonian gravitational N-body model for each type of galaxy I should plot the gravitational function and the tensor for example for poisons equation the potential and the density profile for each type of galaxy.

From “galactic dynamics” [81] if we now sum up all of the contributions " δW ", there is an expression for the potential energy,

$$W = -\frac{1}{8\pi G} \int d^3x |\nabla\Phi|^2 \tag{Eq 68)}$$

To obtain an alternative expression for W , we again apply the divergence theorem and replace $\nabla^2\phi$ by $4\pi G\rho$ to obtain

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \int d^3x \rho(x)\Phi(x) \tag{Eq 69)}$$

The potential-energy tensor In §4.8.3 we shall encounter the tensor W that is defined by

$$W_{jk} = G \int d^3x \rho(x) x_j \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial x_k} \tag{Eq 70)}$$

where ρ and Φ are the density and potential of some body, and the integral is to be taken over all space. We now deduce some useful properties of W , which is known as the Chandrasekhar potential-energy tensor. 2 If we substitute for Φ from equation (2.3), W becomes

$$W_{jk} = G \int d^3x \rho(x) x_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \int \frac{d^3x' \rho(x')}{|x' - x|} \quad \text{Eq 71)$$

Galaxies in general:

For flat rotation curves, the velocity function takes a similar form to the stability equation from magnetic levitator solution. Flat rotation curves imply that the stability criteria is met and although this is not exhibited for all galaxies it is possible that the rotation curves could be produced because of the active error correction between some balancing forces such in this case of the magnet is gravity and the electromagnetic field.

An illustrative representation encapsulating the galactic rotation curve data, which has proven insightful for elucidating the dynamics of dark matter's influence on visible matter within galactic distributions, is notably provided by Begeman, Broelis, and Sanders [82]. This image served as a foundational reference, guiding the formulation of expectations regarding force strength and fostering a deeper understanding of the interplay between dark matter and the observable matter within galactic structures.

The data presented in their study reveals a discernible discrepancy between empirical observations and theoretical predictions, as dictated by the Newtonian approximation. Given the well-established accuracy of the general theory of relativity in describing gravitational dynamics, substantiated by numerous measurements and acknowledged corrections, it is regarded as the fundamental framework from which our models ought to be derived.

Solving the N-K Einstein field equations, with its $NK_{\mu\nu}$ components for each tensor, alongside the intricate derivations and operations involved for each tensor element, appears to be a formidable task beyond the reach of conventional computational capabilities. Consequently, in pursuit of practicality, deriving Newtonian approximations becomes imperative to elucidate the gravitational field for situations of significance.

In our computations for modeling gravitational fields, we will employ the weak field limit from general relativity, which precisely corresponds to the Newtonian approximation. Numerous studies have demonstrated the equivalence of gravitomagnetism to general relativity. An example of such exploration is found in the work titled "Galactic Dynamics in General Relativity: The Role of Gravitomagnetism" authored by Matteo Luca Ruggiero, Antonello Ortolan, and Clive C. Speake [83]. Additionally, another relevant contribution involves deriving density functions through Green's theorem, as exemplified in the paper "Galactic Rotation Curve According to Gravitomagnetism" by Ludwig, G.O. [84]. Combining insights from both works provides a comprehensive understanding. The synthesis of vector field plots for each scenario promises to yield a more comprehensive and nuanced depiction of the gravitational dynamics under consideration.

The best thing to do is place approximations on the forces. There are 3 other papers on this. Why hasn't someone else done this exact thing defining dark matter and the fields of dark matter? Frame dragging and other relativistic effects were postulated first by Oliver Heaviside which was before relativity was developed. It seems likely that then that the theory of relativity can be derived from nonlinear coordinate transforms or something acting on the gravitomagnetic equations.

Frame dragging measured from gravity probe B shows that on the small scale the gravitomagnetic effects exist and there's a minute frame dragging and this paper along with other known papers in literature shows that the frame dragging is merely a relativistic effect of the motion of the mass since it gives a perceived current. Instead of measuring the field from the gyroscopes outside of Earth, we would need much larger or different tools to accurately measure the force felt on the system. But exactly what tools? How can this be measured and how can these things be calculated and experiments created to show? What is the exact nature of this force? One might need new tools to measure these parts of the field similar to how new tools are needed to measure magnetic currents relative to electric currents. Is there a way to prove that dark matter relative to our position and velocity in the Milky Way from which we make our observations can be formed by summing the effects of the dark stars relative to the visible matter? What would the definitions of the dark stars tell us about the differences in processes for the dark electron and dark neutron degeneracy pressures which are preventing the dark stars at the end of their life from collapsing into dark black holes? Why can't we see the explosions and collapses of dark stars?

Is there a measureable wobble or other motion induced in the vicinity on visible objects that could be used to calculate the gravitomagnetic force by another means? It is possible to do this by proving the N body solution converges to the density solution for each density case. The normal force would be like a top and it would cause wobble as well as potentially a distortion in the geometry called galactic warping. I think the best way to simulate this theory is to test the electromagnetic version of it with particles but also by simulation. Maybe we can get a gyroscope that has a controllable shell shape with a negatively charged gas within the hollow part and a positively charged pole in the center.

As the top spins a magnetic field is generated by the gas and the magnetic field in turn acts on the gyroscope. If the shape is controllable maybe it's possible to emulate this experiment to collect data on the exact small scale effects from the relation to electromagnetic theory. The field near earth must be weak but near the galaxies would be large.

Hypothesis: Stabilization of the gravitational force occurs when the gravitoelectric field is equal to the gravitomagnetic part of the field times the velocity and this occurs physically when stars are in circular orbits around the galactic nucleus.

Plot all equations plot GEM and EM equations for electron how it changes for scaling. This model causes induced current which might be perceived as dark current similar to the direct relation for holes and electrons with $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}_{induced} = \vec{J}_{induced}$. The dark current creates a gravitational field and we can plot this field but in the relativistic framework there is no point to call it dark current since it can just be viewed as the induced current by the motion of the mass. With a cyclotron in GEM the equation is $F = m_s B_g v \sin(\theta)$ where B_g is the gravitomagnetic part

of the gravitational field. Using the fact that $c^2 = \frac{1}{\mu_0 \epsilon_0}$ and $\frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} = G$ we can write the permittivity of free space for the gravitational equations for the equivalence to Maxwell's equations as: $\epsilon_{0g} = \frac{1}{4\pi G}$, and the gravitomagnetic permissivity of free space: $\mu_{0g} = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2}$. The Lienard Wiechert magnetic field equation would give $\vec{B}_g = \frac{Gmv}{c^2} \left(\frac{\hat{r}'}{|\hat{r}'|^2} \right)$ the gravitomagnetic force would be given by: $\vec{F} = \frac{Gm_s^2 v_s^2}{c^2} \left(\frac{\hat{r}}{r^2} \right)$ and for the sun with $m_s = 1.9 * 10^{30} kg$ and $v_s = 250,000 \left(\frac{m}{s} \right)$, $\vec{F} = (5.45 * 10^{52}) \left(\frac{\hat{r}}{r^2} \right)$.

Subsequently, the equations governing the interactions among the k bodies can be defined utilizing a straightforward k-body Newtonian formulation. It is conceivable, however, that to arrive at a comprehensive solution for the total gravitational field, it may be necessary to plot the individual fields contributed by each of the k bodies. Having obtained the total fields for each galaxy, we can then employ this information to compute the relative contributions of clusters and assess alterations to the virial theorem. The approximation in question would involve employing the z transform and can be facilitated through the error function relation elucidated above, measuring the discrepancies between observed data and our theoretical equations.

Notably, despite the absence of dark matter in the initial considerations, the exact force equations now allow for the definition of dark matter within the framework of the force field equations. It is pertinent to acknowledge an alternative method for deriving these equations, namely the Biot-Savart law, which we intend to utilize for verification purposes. It is noteworthy that no relativistic factors have been observed, contrary to initial expectations in cases involving stars with exceptionally large radii that might approach or exceed the speed of light.

The apparent overshoot in the system of bodies suggests stabilization around a particular velocity. To corroborate our calculations, we intend to incorporate the Biot-Savart law, ensuring the robustness of our results. Notably, the absence of relativistic factors, contrary to expectations in cases of stars with large radii, highlights the system's stability. As observed in general Newtonian calculations for spherical systems, such as those detailed in "Galactic Dynamics" by James Binney and Scott Tremaine [see page 61, spherical systems, July 2007] **[85]**, the gravitational potential of spherically symmetric matter distributions can be calculated utilizing Newton's theorems, demonstrating the efficacy of foundational principles in gravitational dynamics.

Newton's first theorem posits that a body situated within a spherical shell of matter experiences no net gravitational force emanating from that shell. In tandem, Newton's second theorem asserts that the gravitational force acting on a body positioned outside a spherical shell of matter is identical to what it would be if all the mass within the shell were concentrated at a singular point located at its center.

Leveraging Newton's law of gravity, and in alignment with Newton's Second Theorem, which stipulates that the gravitational force external to a closed spherical shell of matter is equivalent to that arising from a point concentration of mass at its center, the velocity $v(R)$ of stars

within a galaxy—depicted as a function of the distance R from the galactic center, also known as rotation curves—is described by Newton's law, assuming circular motion. This insight is drawn from the document "Introduction to Cosmology and Dark Matter," specifically documented in page 163, section 5.1.2, under the heading "Galaxies." **[86]**

$$v(R) = \sqrt{\frac{GM(R)}{R}} \quad M(R) = 4\pi \int_0^R \rho(r)r^2 dr, \quad \text{Eq 72)}$$

Here $\rho(r)$ is the mass density. The contribution to ρ from luminous matter would lead to $v(r) \propto R^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ at large R . But observationally, one has $v(R)$ ' constant, see Fig. 6. Explaining the observed rotation curves requires more matter abundance, and differently distributed, than the visible one: a constant rotation curve requires $MDM \propto R$, which is attained for a DM density distribution $\rho_{DM}(r) \propto 1/r^{-2}$.

If we assume circular motion but that there is an additional force that acts on the body equal to the gravitomagnetic force generated by the large scale matter current or the motion of the density profile, then Newton's equations become from the field created by the current:

$$\frac{v^2}{r} = \frac{GM(R)}{R} - \frac{1}{c^2 \epsilon_{g0}} \left(\frac{M(R)v^2}{4\pi R^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 73)}$$

This equation can be used to find the stability point, or the location for which the velocities become balanced by the forces becoming balanced. Which by moving the magnetic term to the LHS and pulling out the velocity term becomes:

$$\left(\frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{c^2 \epsilon_{g0}} \left(\frac{M(R)}{4\pi R^2} \right) \right) v^2 = \frac{GM(R)}{R}$$

Some algebra yields:

$$v = \sqrt{\left(\frac{GM(R)}{R} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{R} + \frac{1}{c^2 \epsilon_{g0}} \left(\frac{M(R)}{4\pi R^2} \right)} \right)}$$

Finding a common denominator gives:

$$v = \sqrt{\left(\frac{4\pi GRc^2 \epsilon_{g0} M(R)}{4\pi Rc^2 \epsilon_{g0} + M(R)} \right)} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{GM(R)}{1 + \frac{M(R)}{4\pi Rc^2 \epsilon_{g0}}} \right)} \quad \text{Eq 74)}$$

Now, defining the mass in terms of the density this becomes:

$$v = \sqrt{\left(\frac{4\pi G \int_0^R \rho(r)r^2 dr,}{1 + \frac{\int_0^R \rho(r)r^2 dr,}{Rc^2\epsilon_{g0}}} \right)} \quad \text{Eq 75)}$$

Total mass from virial theorem Zwicky; Smith. For a self-gravitating system in equilibrium, kinetic energy (T) and potential energy (V) are related by the virial theorem with $2T + V = 0$. The kinetic energy is defined as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \sum_i m_i v_i^2 \quad \text{Eq 76)}$$

Potential Energy:

$$V = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{Gm_i m_j}{r_{ij}} \quad \text{Eq 77)}$$

The provided text does not contain specific details or a publication source. However, if you are referring to a particular source that discusses the inclusion of the gravitomagnetic field in the assumptions for deriving the virial theorem, please provide the necessary details, and I can assist you in creating a proper citation.

$$\langle T \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \langle \sum_i \mathbf{F}_i \cdot \mathbf{r}_i \rangle \quad \text{Eq 78)}$$

The force here is given by the Lorentz force law for gravitodynamics:

$$\vec{F} = -\nabla\phi - GM(V \times \vec{B}_g) \quad \text{Eq 79)}$$

The potential energy equation here becomes modified to include the forces generated by the matter current in the gravitational field:

$$V = -\frac{1}{2} \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{Gm_i m_j}{r_{ij}} \quad \text{Eq 80)}$$

$$\langle \frac{1}{2} \sum_i m_i v_i^2 \rangle = -\frac{1}{2} \langle \sum_i ((-\nabla\phi_i - m_i(v_i \times \vec{B}_{gi})) \cdot \vec{r}_i) \rangle \quad \text{Eq 81)}$$

In a functional relationship where velocity (v) is contingent upon the masses denoted as m sub I and m sub j, it is conceivable that the necessity of employing mass as a function of radius in these equations can be circumvented. Instead, adopting a simplified approach by using a singular large mass to represent the galactic center (denoted as "large m") is a viable option. Preliminary plots employing this modified equation have demonstrated the convergence of values for larger radii toward a singular radius. The introduction of a variable mass density profile is anticipated to enhance the precision of these computations.

In essence, it is imperative to substantiate and employ the equations already selected. For instance, the virial theorem, as presented above, operates under the assumption of a potential function, yet it fails to incorporate the gravitomagnetic vector potential component of the field.

The applicability of the virial theorem hinges on the underlying system structure and the fields involved. A self-gravitating system in equilibrium necessitates the inclusion of the velocity-dependent term, the relativistic gravitational field term, or, notably, the gravitomagnetic field. The gravitomagnetic field can be interpreted as a relativistic consequence resulting from the motion of mass, signifying the existence of a matter current originating from the singular mass. To advance the comprehensiveness of the theoretical framework, it is crucial to incorporate and validate these additional terms in the equations, ensuring a more accurate portrayal of the system's dynamics.

The modified virial theorem, upon application, reveals that the total mass of a cluster surpasses the observed values, suggesting a need for the gravitomagnetic term to subtract mass from the virial theorem. This adjustment is facilitated by the equivalence of the gravitomagnetic term in the gravitodynamic framework to the dark mass in the Newtonian framework. While the Newtonian framework encompasses the Coulomb-like potential derived from electrostatics, it lacks the additional force terms originating from the gravitomagnetic force—a consequence of the reformulation of Newton's theory in multivariable calculus and its equivalence to Coulomb field theory.

These effects, although challenging to measure due to scaling requirements, are inherently constrained by the mathematical operations defining electromagnetic theory. The presence of an Ampere term, pivotal in Maxwell's derivation of the Maxwell wave equation, seems to be a missing link, along with the dynamic effects associated with a moving mass. The discovery of gravitational waves implies that the Newtonian approximation ($v \ll c$) to gravitodynamics takes on the Maxwell equation form, resembling the uncoupled wave equations for the magnetic and electric potential in the gravitoelectric and gravitomagnetic fields. This insight underscores the intrinsic connection between the gravitational and electromagnetic aspects of the theoretical framework. Alternate form of the expression could $G_{electric} = G_E$, $G_{magnetic} = G_B$, so at least it kind of at least looks like the usual newtonian theory with its own constants but that the subscripts remind us where the core lemma and mathematical theorems are that build the B and E field parts of the G field.

If the total energy function of the system can be precisely defined, an exploration into Noether's work becomes imperative to establish the existence of conservation laws for dark energy. However, determining the energy function for dark energy poses a pivotal question.

To address this, it becomes apparent that modifications to the virial theorem are necessary. Incorporating the gamma factor and accounting for the usual relativistic effects becomes a prerequisite before contemplating further adjustments to accommodate the intricacies associated with dark energy.

Density Profile #1

Navarro, Frenk and White (NFW) profile [87] given by

$$\rho_{NFW}(r) = \rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \quad \text{Eq 88)}$$

where in the Milky Way $r_s = 19.6$ kpc and $\rho_s = 0.32$ GeV/cm³.

With this density profile, the potential energy tensor is:

$$W_{jk} = G \int d^3x \rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{x} \right) \left(1 + \frac{x}{r_s} \right)^{-2} x_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \int \frac{d^3x' \rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{x'} \right) \left(1 + \frac{x'}{r_s} \right)^{-2}}{|x' - x|} \quad \text{Eq 89)}$$

$$v = \sqrt{\left(\frac{4\pi G \int_0^R \left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right) r^2 dr,}{\int_0^R \left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right) r^2 dr,} \right)} \quad \text{Eq 90)}$$

$$1 + \frac{\int_0^R \left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right) r^2 dr,}{Rc^2 \epsilon_{g0}}$$

Therefore fore the milky way with the gravitomagnetic terms, the equations become:

The gravitational and magnetic and magnetic field potential as well as the space-time can be plotted for this case showing the vector field for each of these as well as the potential function. The density profiles can be plotted as well as the potential energy functions and the velocity functions.

We can use the Maxwell equations to obtain the differential equations for E and B and use the differential equation solver to solve for E and B numerically from the differential equation. Ultimately this is an inhomogeneous electromagnetic wave equation we obtain when we uncouple the equations.

We have Poisson's equation:

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2}}{\epsilon_{g0}} \quad \text{Eq 91)}$$

By equivalence of gravitodynamics Earnshaw's Theorem, A particle with mass cannot be held in stable equilibrium by gravitoelectric forces alone. The solutions here are given by greens functions:

$$\phi(r) = \iiint_{R_3} \frac{\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r'} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r'}{r_s} \right)^{-2}}{4\pi \epsilon_{g0} |r' - r|} dV \quad \text{Eq 92)}$$

And then we can find the equation for the gravitoelectric field from gravitoelectrostatics:

$$\vec{\nabla} \phi = \vec{E}, \quad \text{Eq 93)}$$

But the problem here is that there is a current term and this is from the other maxwell equations so we must uncouple the equations by combining them to get the differential equation for the electric field that we need to solve:

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E} = - \frac{\left(\left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right) \right)}{\epsilon} \quad \text{Eq 94)}$$

Truly this is a subject of establishing the Helmholtz equation for the magnetic field as well as the electric field so that we can use the greens function solution to these equations. Then we can directly insert the solutions for E and B into the differential equations for A and ϕ so to plot the full scenario for each of the density profiles. Now, using the gauss law for gravitoelectricity above and amperes law into the curl of the faraday-maxwell law, and using the curl of the curl identity, where ∇^2 is the laplacian:

$$\nabla \times \vec{E} = - \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad \text{Eq 95)}$$

This gives the wave equation for the electric field:

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \vec{E} = - \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_{0g}} \nabla \left(\left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right) \right) + \mu_{0g} \frac{\partial \vec{J}}{\partial t} \right) \quad \text{Eq 96)}$$

Then we can solve for the current density in the above Helmholtz equation for the magnetic field with

$$\frac{\partial \left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \vec{J} = 0 \quad \text{Eq 97)}$$

Then taking the curl of the second equation and inserting the Maxwell equation in for the magnetic field gives:

$$\nabla \times \vec{B} = - \left(\mu_{0g} \vec{J} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \right) \quad \text{Eq 98)}$$

Then we should take the curl of the second equation here and insert the first one into it

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \vec{B} = - \left(\mu_{0g} \nabla \times \vec{J} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \nabla \times \vec{E}}{\partial t} \right) = - \mu_{0g} \nabla \times \vec{J} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} \quad \text{Eq 99)}$$

Which is a separable differential equation. We can obtain a solution to this equation for each component of the vector J and then insert this into the Helmholtz equation to get the full picture for the magnetic field.

Now also we can use the inhomogeneous wave equations for the potential functions as well by uncoupling the potential versions of the Maxwell laws

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \phi = \frac{\left(\rho_s \left(\frac{r_s}{r} \right) \left(1 + \frac{r}{r_s} \right)^{-2} \right)}{\epsilon_{go}} \quad \text{Eq 100)}$$

And

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{A}}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \vec{A} = \mu_{0g} \vec{J} \quad \text{Eq 101)}$$

And the solution to the vector potential is given by:

$$\vec{A}(r, t) = \iiint \frac{\vec{J}(r', t - \frac{r}{c})}{4\pi\epsilon_0 g c^2 r'} dV' \quad \text{Eq 102)}$$

Upon solving the presented equations, comprehensive insights into the field plots corresponding to various density profiles are acquired. Subsequently, the subsequent steps involve solving and plotting the electric and magnetic fields, along with the vector potential and scalar potential fields. The objective is to systematically explore all conceivable density distributions to assess their compatibility with the established hypotheses.

The scope of this research primarily involves formulating hypotheses and identifying potential models accounting for the observed forces. Considering the necessity to systematically assess numerous density distributions and conduct extensive calculations across a substantial dataset, the depth required for detailed calculations, derivations, and simulations suggests that a subsequent project or paper dedicated explicitly to these aspects would be more appropriate.

Density Profile #2

The Einasto density profile [88] given by

$$\rho_{Ein}(r) = \rho_s e^{-\frac{2}{\alpha} \left(\left(\frac{r}{r_s} \right)^\alpha - 1 \right)} \quad \text{Eq 89)}$$

where in the Milky Way $\alpha = 0.22$, $r_s = 16.07$ kpc and $\rho_s = 0.11$ GeV/cm³.

Density Profile #3

The Burkert profile [89] given by

$$\rho_{NFW}(r) = \frac{\rho_s}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{r_s}{r}\right)\right) \left(1 + \left(\frac{r_s}{r}\right)^2\right)} \quad \text{Eq 90)}$$

where in the Milky Way $r_s = 9.26$ kpc and $\rho_s = 1.57 \frac{\text{GeV}}{\text{cm}^3}$. With this profile, the dark matter density in the galactic center is smoother.

From this data what is the metric tensor for the gravity, what about the Energy Tensor, Riemann tensor, for the galaxy? What are the N-body equations and the geodesic equations and the equations which produce the density, mass and velocity components? What are the differential equations that produce these density profiles?

Additional Forces that might be present in the Newtonian Model

MOND shows that modified potentials can be used to achieve the galactic rotation curves so in general ignoring the gravitomagnetic terms, the modified potential may be written as:

$$V(r) = \sum_{\alpha}^k \frac{A_{\alpha}}{r^{\alpha}} \quad \text{Eq 110)}$$

In my opinion this doesn't really solve the problem at hand even though MOND can be used to essentially solve the galactic rotation curve problem. The major issue is that Newtonian physics as with all physics generally calls for a description of the extra force terms. It seems like

a good start to solve the problem and actually MOND is what led me to write this paper since the possibility was proven to exist that modified potentials could solve the rotation curve problem. Usually we have a way to know why the extra force terms would exist but in MOND it is not clear what might cause the modified potentials to exist and why it is even justified in the first place other than it matches observations what forces are responsible for the observed effect. This led me ultimately to investigate whether relativistic metrics could produce the same modified potentials.

The central inquiry of this paper pertains to the generalization of the Kepler differential equation within the context of the two-body problem. This involves introducing an additional term in the gravitational potential, along with the incorporation of the gravitomagnetic force term. The concluding aspect of this investigation aims to derive the shape profiles resulting from cluster contributions, taking into consideration potential gravitational and gravitomagnetic effects.

The temporal dimension is intricately linked to the variable θ , with the transformation of θ providing a direct correlation to time. The insights gleaned from this analysis enable the formulation of the Newtonian differential equation, a critical step in obtaining orbital solutions. Subsequently, integration over these initial conditions becomes essential to ascertain the galaxy shapes, conceptualizing differential equations as operators acting on initial condition spaces.

Exploiting the established relationship between shape and density, the definition of electric and magnetic fields as functions of mass density and matter current density ensues, drawing from the Biot-Savart law. The resolution of the first Maxwell equation for Laplace's equation for the electric field, employing the density function, facilitates the depiction of the gravitational field and potential. This comprehensive approach enables a nuanced exploration of the gravitational aspects of the field, thereby contributing to a more profound understanding of galactic structures. There are k density distributions for each of the k galaxies which leads to k Gauss law equations. Each of the n stars in each galaxy as well satisfy the Poisson equation:

$$\nabla^2 \phi_n = \rho_n \quad \text{Eq 111)}$$

Then the Lorentz force law requires considering all the forces from each of the galaxies

$$\vec{F} = \sum_{n=1}^{n=N} \left(m_n \vec{E}_n + m_n (v_n \times \vec{B}_T) \right) + \sum_{k=1}^K \vec{F}_{kthgalaxy} \quad \text{Eq 112)}$$

Generally,

$$\vec{E}_n = -\vec{\nabla} \phi_n - \vec{r} \dot{A} \quad \text{Eq 113)}$$

And

$$\phi_n(r) = \sum_{\alpha}^n \frac{A_{n\alpha}}{r^\alpha} \quad \text{Eq 114)}$$

So this is how we can solve for the electric field as long as we define each constant for the matrix of constants A.

$$\vec{E}_n = -\nabla \left(\sum_{\alpha}^n \frac{A_{n\alpha}}{r^\alpha} \right) \quad \text{Eq 115)}$$

And if the clusters are far enough away in the galaxy the gravitomagnetic effect would be negligible and the higher order in the terms for the potential can be ignored since they are not within close enough range to be affected by the shape since the orbits are stable and the forces symmetrically act approximately on the galaxy. The relative velocity between the clusters might be important in some cases and can not be ignored. In those cases we would have to add an extra term but initially the Newtonian force inserted into $\vec{F}_{kthgalaxy}$ gives the equation of motion:

$$\vec{F} = \frac{d^2r}{dt^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{n=N} \left(m_n \left(-\nabla \left(\sum_{\alpha}^n \frac{A_{n\alpha}}{r^\alpha} \right) \right) + \frac{m_n \mu_{0g}}{4\pi} \left(v_n \times \left(\iiint_V \frac{\mathbf{J} dV}{|\mathbf{r}'|^3} \right) \right) \right) + \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{G(\sum m_n)M_k}{r_k^2} \quad \text{Eq 116)}$$

Where $M_k = \sum m_k$ the sum of the k small masses that compose the kth galaxy. It is also possible that the gravitomagnetic forces that are missing are from the relative motions of the clusters. If that were the case then the linearized Einstein field equations for the cluster contribution would be for the radial component:

$$\frac{d^2r}{dt^2} = \sum_{n=1}^{n=N} \left(m_n \left(-\nabla \left(\sum_{\alpha}^n \frac{A_{n\alpha}}{r^\alpha} \right) \right) + \frac{m_n \mu_{0g}}{4\pi} \left(v_n \times \left(\iiint_V \frac{\mathbf{J} dV}{|\mathbf{r}'|^3} \right) \right) \right) + \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{G(\sum m_n)M_k}{r_k^2} + \sum \frac{m_k \mu_{0g}}{4\pi} \left(v_k \times \left(\iiint_{V_k} \frac{\mathbf{J}_k dV_k}{|\mathbf{r}_k'|^3} \right) \right) \quad \text{Eq 117)}$$

r_k is the distance between the galaxies, V_k is the volume within the kth galaxy J_k . As we increase in scaling to view the cluster, and super clusters that contain clusters and super super clusters that contain super clusters the Einstein addition of velocity formula will eventually apply. Let us ignore this fact for a second, and only try to measure the relative velocities between objects:

$$v_{super\ super\ cluster} = v_{super\ cluster} + v_{cluster} + v_{galaxy} + v_{sun} + v_{earth} \quad \text{Eq 118)}$$

If we are stationary on the earth. And doing some research, $v_{earth} = \frac{30,000m}{s}$, $v_{sun} = 250,000 \frac{m}{s}$, Andromeda is moving towards milky way at 300m/s and in general there may exist cases in the extra galactic frame with velocities for the $v_{galaxy} = 600,000 m/s$, $v_{galaxy} = 300,000$. The Milky Way and Andromeda are in the local group cluster and the local group cluster is within the Virgo super cluster. The velocity of the Virgo cluster relative to the local super cluster. The local super cluster is otherwise known as the local group or local cluster. Another name for the local super cluster is Virgo super cluster. The velocity of the Virgo cluster relative to the local

cluster is: $v_{cluster} = \frac{400,000m}{s}$ and the Virgo super cluster is a part of the Laniakea Super cluster. The great attractor is the theoretical center point of the Laniakea super cluster. It has been measured that these velocities. And apparently it has been measured that the great attractor is moving relatively to the shapely super cluster.

As an adjustment to this section, it might be necessary that the forces from the clusters and super clusters on the galaxies have to be accommodated for as well.

I read a paper that stated the recession velocities here to be of the magnitude 15,000,000m/s, and now we are getting somewhere! This is 5 percent of the speed of light and we are not even on the largest scale not to mention probably not even selecting the largest velocities of the samples of clusters within the observable universe. This means that there are more than likely many cases in which increased scaling implies that there are 5% on the lower bound but maybe even up to 20% or more the speed of light. Now if we select super clusters as far away from this Laniakea super cluster as possible then we can see the highest relative velocity of those places within the universe to see if this number is relativistic. If the number is relativistic we actually have to use Einstein's equations to transform the velocities as we change the scaling. Is this cluster within other clusters? How long does that possibility continue? Does this occur outside of our observable universe? Apparently other astronomical places where relativity would come into play is with relativistic stars that are ejected out of black holes. As the scaling increases, the velocity increases and therefore the relative effect of the gravitomagnetic force. Since it is known that they are gravitationally bound it must be true that these terms have to be added into the equations for the velocity calculations.

Is the k th galaxies current density induced by the relative velocity between the galaxies. It is also fair to say that if there is a super cluster that contains clusters of galaxies that move relative to the super cluster center while there are galaxies moving relative to the cluster cores in the super cluster. The super clusters could then provide a way to measure the dynamics of the effects of scaling in gravity. It is potentially possible if the universe exists outside of our own bubble of perception that this nested algorithm of clusters within larger clusters could continue on and on. But the problem one has naturally is eventually the effects of the higher order terms of relativity will become required and then the linearized equations no longer hold in which case better metrics would need developed as well as equations to fit those scenarios but there is no reason why the theory of relativity could not be extended to the scale of positive infinity.

If the galaxies become very near and close together the situation is more chaotic and there are going to be interaction terms between the galactic cores and the stars as the core of one galaxy passes near enough to that of another galaxy. By the discrete sum representation to integral transform the acceleration can be written as integrals in time as well as the coordinates. This allows us to use the data we collect and do something like a z transform on the large amount of data to obtain the correct theory.

It may also be possible that if the telescope is moving around the spinning earth another coordinate transformation similar to that of the coordinate transform to zoom into the electrons perspective would transform the coordinates that we have of the equations because we are

observing it with a relative velocity. Then the light information is transformed by the lens and the algorithms of the computer to display on our screen the correct information from the observations.

Now if there is the possibility outside of our universe that there are super super clusters which contain super clusters and a super super cluster nuclei which has super clusters which contain clusters of galaxies that each move around their clusters cluster nuclei, the equation becomes:

Then after all that we can add extra dimensions and make the coordinates and the fields are n dimensional. As the clusters get closer together there will be interaction terms between the densities but this can be interpreted as star-star interaction terms even though many stars will initially pass through the empty space. In some collisions some stars will be eaten by the supermassive black hole at the center of the other galaxy.

Now that we have the differential equations, we can fit them with solutions given by the Taylor series since we have the initial conditions for the velocities and the accelerations. The n body problem can be solved with Taylor power series and so each of these equations can be solved with a similar power series. The solutions we obtain by power series then should be able to be simulated and give us numerical approximations to the linear order. Then we can repeat this algorithm n times if the universe is infinitely large outside our observation to achieve the relative effect of the motions between the galaxies. And then we can realize that this gives us the rules for howt he scaling changes and try to stitch this together with an integral in the continuous form. If we put this in continuous form then we have the fifth variable effect on scaling which essentially is parameterized by n scaling changes. PID controllers, as from Z. Gao's "Active Disturbance Rejection Control," [90] have the following solution:

$$u = k_p + k_1 \int edt + k_d \dot{e}$$

Eq 119)

The above equation represents a series RLC load which has control parameters k_p, k_1, k_d . Controlling these circuit parameters controls the current draw, and therefore controls the voltage in the load that does the lifting of the ball. In the flat, linear system modeled by the Thompson Ring Experiment, the control parameters are manually controlled. One should expect that in the nonlinear case, this would be extraordinarily difficult, and that the control parameters might vary in time as would be done for complicated compound processes built from these methods. This is effectively achieved by controlling the gain of the operational amplifier.

If multiple electromagnets were added in series, there would be inductive terms in the plant transfer function. This type of circuit, if designed properly could be that of controlling the trajectory of magnetic balls within tubes, much like which occurs for the intrinsic magnetic dipoles of the charged particles which are accelerated within the acceleration chambers at CERN.

The primary purpose of this paper is to develop a robust framework that employs error functions similar to those used for PID control algorithms to quantitatively determine the requirements for the linearized form of the theory of relativity capable of modeling dark matter-related phenomena and to construct any possible variations of relativity if any such modified

theory be necessary. In the flat curve cases the velocity functions occur as a result of stabilization between forces. In control theory the error function $e(r) = v_{observed}(r) - v_{Newtonian}(r)$ gives the difference between the setpoint $v_{observed}(r)$ and the process variable $v_{Newtonian}(r)$. The differential between velocities in observed and theoretical velocities give us the ability to model the induced gravitational field between the newtonian theory and observations because of the stability conditions to use the PID definition of the voltage: $\phi(r) = K_p e(r) + K_i \int_0^r e(t) dt + K_d \left(\frac{de(r)}{dr} \right)$. The values K_p K_i and K_d should be determined essentially from fitting the error function to the observations between the theory. From Maxwells equations, $\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t}$ can be written as: $\vec{\nabla} \times (\vec{\nabla} \phi(r)) = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t}$. If we make these assumptions where Electric field is replaced with the gravitational field and the electric potential is replaced with the gravitational potential then we have a method to fit the data from the observations to the calculations from the extra forces from gravitomagnetism. It should be noted that this fitting should occur after we correct the Newtonian model to accommodate for cluster forces and extra galactic forces. Usually these functions are functions of time but since the radius is a function of time this actually can be written as a function of time.

It is possible that the method above gives us constraints to the mass density profiles and we can predict the modified mass density profiles from the error functions as well instead of adding the extra field term. So in addition to getting the induced gravitomagnetic field, in this frame, the density function is given by Maxwell's first law:

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot (\vec{\nabla} \phi(r)) = \rho_{differential} = \rho_{dark}$$

Eq 120)

The existence of a potential differential between the theories implies that the mass density function will be modified as well as there being an induced gravitomagnetic field. We can use the remaining Maxwell equations essentially to plot these functions now and then this could be compared to the data from the plot of the force functions for the linearized approximation. The gravitational field can be plotted and is the gradient of this function here. The Lagrangian functions can be plotted as well once the functions are determined for each potential approximation. Then from these field equations the trajectories can be calculated by the Euler-Lagrange equations on the potential function. Now the stability functions for physics can be proven using the general transforms and contours to define stability of the system to show that the n body solution can be composed of the noninteracting two body solutions. The stability theorem can be formed even if the matter is dark based on the effects and constraints on effects of real matter. If the galactic center has any motion then things become more complicated since there are additional terms that must be added to accommodate for the additional relative motion. Using Einstein's paper: "2 body problem in general relativity theory, " I think I should use Einstein's other later papers on unified field theory such as Kaluza Klein unified field theory with electricity combined with my theory

It seems that beyond the Schwarzschild boundary #2 which is "complex" that the kinetic energy of the particles would all become potential energy, or essentially there would become another term which acts to balance the equations and is what is responsible for the extra force that would be seen. It is a purely kinetic effect of us the observer on earth taking the measurements

while we are moving around the sun while the sun is moving around the galaxy and we are trying to calculate the velocity of other stars that are moving. Does the second Schwarzschild radius occur because it is an n-k body problem and not a 2 body problem? Does the Schwarzschild radius become modified to need the gravitomagnetic term in the cases where velocity matters? What is the Schwarzschild radius of our galaxy cluster? What is the Schwarzschild radius between two galaxies if you are far enough away?

Is the Schwarzschild radius modified in instances where the gravitomagnetic term is high influence such as if a supermassive black hole was traveling with large velocity near a galaxy or something? Taking this theory to the simplest context, what is the gravitomagnetic effects of a supermassive black hole traveling through the sky? How does the Schwarzschild radius equation and the metric become modified in these different cases? Do all objects such as electrons have a Schwarzschild radius? Schwarzschild radius of electron is $r_s = 1.3 * 10^{-57} m$. This appears to be the smallest radius. The mathematical problem of n gravitational bodies revolving around a galactic nucleus which may be composed of a single supermassive black hole but also with nearby rapidly revolving star systems. Galactic nuclei may be active but also might have

I think in the context of the discovery that the gravitational theory of relativity reduces to the GEM, then the electrodynamical theory of relativity should reduce to the standard theory of Maxwell's equations. But the opposite must be true as well that there should be an analogous relativistic theory for electromagnetism that is casted in the Einstein Field Equations. Then the effects we see from gravitational theory such as Schwarzschild radius in principle with the space-time representation of the electromagnetic field. There should then be an electromagnetic Schwarzschild radius that is different from the gravitational Schwarzschild radius. What is the Schwarzschild radius for complex matter? Maybe the second Schwarzschild radius I am looking for is the electromagnetic Schwarzschild radius? By direct substitution of the equivalence of the theories between Maxwell's and Newtonian for positive masses we can state the electromagnetic Schwarzschild radius: And therefore we can state the space-time representation of the electromagnet theory by defining the Einstein field equations for charge and current density. With the space-time representation of electric charges and electric currents using the field equations we could expect that the Einstein field equations for electromagnetism would take the form:

$$R_{\mu\nu}^{nk} - \frac{1}{2} R e b_{\mu\nu}^{nk} + \Lambda e b_{\mu\nu}^{nk} = \frac{2}{\epsilon_0 c^4} C_{\mu\nu}^{nk} \quad \text{Eq 121)}$$

In the linearized case the equations above reduce to the Maxwell's equations. Eb is the electromagnetic space-time tensor for each of the nk bodies. It is possible that these equations need transformed with the chain rule to see the extra terms. Maybe we should use the matrix form of the field equations and all the equations because Einstein summation was invented in 1916 but matrices didn't become popular until 1920s Using the linearized theory for Newtonian gravity we can state the equivalence to the space-time version of electromagnetic theory. The usual electromagnetic field tensor is related to eb tensor. The tensor C is the electromagnetic energy tensor for relativity theory of electromagnetism.

It is clear that the tensors we defined here are not in direct proportion to that of the Newtonian theory but that the Newtonian theory serves as the basis for the relativistic theory so

that in the limit of linearization, The fundamental principle of Unified Field Theory is directly generalized from general relativities equivalence principle. In the Unified Field Theory, the unified equivalence principle generally states the equivalence of space-time and inertial matter properties. The electromagnetic force as experienced locally while standing on a massive body is the same as the pseudo(relativistic)-force experienced by an observer in a non-inertial (accelerated) frame of reference. This equivalence can only be stated from the fact that the Newtonian equivalence can be stated between the mathematical forms of the theory with simply the replacement of matter and charge in the equations. In other words, the relativistic metrics and cases essentially depend on the Newtonian information but the Newtonian information is modified by the existence of relative motion.

The Lorentz force law can be derived from this version of the geodesic equations and appropriate definitions of the field equations. The electromagnetic space-time metric is but one element to a matrix that contains the other types of space-time metrics such as the strong field, weak field and gravitational field metrics. The Schwarzschild radius of the electron is $1.3 * 10^{-57}$ m.

For the Unified Field Theory representation, the electromagnetic Schwarzschild radius is:

$$r_{es} = \frac{q}{2\pi\epsilon_0 c^2} = \frac{(1.60217663 * 10^{-19})}{2\pi(8.85418782 * 10^{-12})(3 * 10^8)^2} = 3.158 * 10^{-25} \quad \text{Eq 122)}$$

Which means for the electron that the space and time components swap at a value much smaller than the expected electron radius. This value however is much larger than the gravitational Schwarzschild radius. Both of these things relative to us are unobservable, much smaller than the electron radius. This gives better bounds for the particle pair model for the electron supposing it is a particle paired with a virtual particle at some radius much smaller than the electron radius so that the properties of matter could be viewed as a mathematical point or a point object with associated properties and with a rapid motion.

Now on the larger scale let us calculate the Schwarzschild radius for the sun and the electromagnetic radius. Since the net global charge of the sun is about 77 coulombs from electrons carried away from solar wind, we can use this. For the sun the gravitational Schwarzschild radius is 3km, which is well within the radius of the sun which is 695,700,000 meters and the electromagnetic Schwarzschild radius is: .000151789 m. This seems to suggest that the difference between the Schwarzschild radii give a way to view the field contributions from each object.

This seems to imply in the context of the zoom operator that as the scaling factor is changing which essentially is the 5th variable there is an exchange of electromagnetic and gravitational energy in as the 5th variable is varied. The same should be expected to happen for the other properties of matter as well. So, if we zoom in far enough on the electron such that we are in the 4d space time locally which for example where this Schwarzschild radius of the electron is visible we would be able to see that in this frame the electron appears to be like a black hole. We may not be able to go there but we can imagine what the space-time force fields created by each property type. It would seem that there would be a coordinate inversion and the meanings of things would change beyond this radius. So how do we describe what the electron is in this viewpoint

relatively to the observer that views the electron as a black hole? This would be like passing the singularity of the black hole and stepping into the space time beyond that boundary. I have not explored this avenue of thought in full detail but it only seems logical to question what it means to continue zooming past observable boundaries.

And the scaling involved makes it so that the angular velocity matters for the potential and it adds extra negative forces that appears like dark matter. This is essentially the magnetic force of the gravitational field that is present in certain relative velocities.

Hypothesis: relative direction of different types of Schwarzschild radii or the difference between them indicates whether the object is gravitational or electromagnetic. The difference in schwarzschild radius give the range of values for the phenomena.

Hypothesis: The stable solution for galaxies in general relativity with flat rotation curves can be represented as n separate 2 body Schwarzschild solutions where the stars are essentially noninteracting. This allows the N-body Einstein field equations to be solved by summing all the 2 body solutions based on the data we have for each star and running the computer over each star. In other words the initial conditions for each star give n 2body simulations.

This is supported by data and the fact that for disk galaxies many stars are in stable circular orbits about the galactic center. Then this means that we can construct the n body solution from all the data for each star initial conditions and insert each 2 body solution for each position.

Hypothesis: There is a law between the magnitude of the Electromagnetic energy spacetime and gravitational spacetime that only comes into play in highly relativistic cases where the space-time energies convert between types so not to surpass the magnitudes set by the system and the constraints imposed by relativity. This law is dependent on the 5th variable.

Hypothesis: given the law between the electromagnetic energy and gravitational energy and the Einstein equivalent of Maxwell's equations, it must be true that there is a connection between the wave function from quantum electrodynamics and the 5d space-time representation in unified field theory.

Hypothesis: quantum space-time representations of the electromagnetic field from quantum electrodynamics is equivalent with UFT description to a transformation in the 5th variable of the electromagnetic space time representation of the theory of electrodynamics of the electron.

Hypothesis: initial conditions of the point objects motions are unknown and immeasurable which is why the exact form of the quantum space-time fields produce the apparently random macroscopic motions of the electron in the de Broglie-bohm theory of particles having definitive trajectories in space-time. In other words, the randomness of quantum mechanics in this model of the electron is stored in the random initial conditions of its periodic motion that corresponds to its structure. This hypothesis corresponds to the Einstein like viewpoint of particle physics. The equations are essentially unsolvable but they could be simulated over all possible variations to produce the total probabilities of the events as according to quantum mechanics.

If galaxies have a shape then they must be in a stable state because they would otherwise be in unstable and chaotic states if there was no well-defined shape because the stars are flying around on more random trajectories from for example collision of a nearby galaxy. In the stable state it is fair to make assumptions about the density profiles as well as the functions used. We may define the error function which corrects the Newtonian term simply as:

$$v_{actual} = v_{observed} - v_{newtonian} \quad \text{Eq 123)}$$

Gravitodynamics with Error Function

For the simplest disk case. Plotting field of visible matter, plotting dark matter gravity field, plotting error function field, velocity field and error function velocity field. Generalizing to arbitrary galaxy shapes and data: select handful of galaxies and measured curves to compare to and for each Plotting field of visible matter, plotting dark matter gravity field, plotting error function field, velocity field and error function velocity field The only way to verify this is completely is to either have the program run over all data for galaxy profiles using the fitting process used for the above cases. I can try to get this data but it may not be avail in database of rotation curve data. I could download it and have the program run over the data to test it for each case. I can manually do that but the point of this work was to determine the method and pass it on. Im not that interested in waiting a while to see other people check it. If the program works we can just get on with it. It seems like a simple program but if it's not this can be done at a later time. Maybe it can be gotten from SPARC or someplace else. Part of this project could be manually finding the correct database so the program can run those algorithms on the correct data relevant to this solution. First the program has to build the language solution then the equation search then equation solving then data acquisition then data analysis with equations and conclusions.

Hypothesis: dark matter map: The error term can give field plots for the vector field for the gravitational field and these plots are equivalent to the gravitomagnetic correction terms resulting from the expanding universe and the presence of a gravitomagnetic field in all of space as shown in the dark energy section next.

If there exists a constant negative energy pressure everywhere in space that corresponds to a vector valued force field in 3 dimensions. If the negative energy is Gravitomagnetic energy, then If there is a constant energy everywhere in the universe that is responsible for the universes' acceleration.

Hypothesis: Dark energy is relativistic Gravitomagnetic energy that exists from the expansion of the universe. If the matter in the universe is expanding then the density function or map would correspond to matter currents. The existence of matter currents implies the existence of gravitomagnetic fields. The energy density of Dark Matter has been estimated to be $u = 6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ J/m}^3$. For the Newtonian approximation, the estimate of the magnitude of the gravitomagnetic field can be found from the energy density equation for the energy stored in a gravitomagnetic field. The energy per unit volume in a region of space of permeability μ_0 containing a gravitomagnetic field B_G is: $u = \frac{B_G^2}{2\mu_0}$. Then the simple equality can be made: $B_G^2 = 2\mu_0 u$ or $B_G = \sqrt{2\mu_0 u}$, and substituting the energy density for dark energy, $B_G = \sqrt{2\mu_0 u} = \sqrt{2\mu_0 (6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ J/m}^3)}$. Now, if we let $\frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_{g0}} = G$, then from the gravitomagnetic wave equation,

the gravitomagnetic permeability can be defined from: $\frac{1}{c^2} = \frac{1}{\mu_{g0}\epsilon_{g0}}$ where $\mu_{g0} = \frac{1}{c^2\epsilon_{g0}} = \frac{4\pi G}{c^2}$, then

$$B_G = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G}{c^2} (6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ J/m}^3)} = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi (6.674 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N} \cdot \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{kg}^2})}{(299,792,458 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}})^2} (6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ J/m}^3)} =$$

$$\sqrt{8\pi (4.4555 \times 10^{-37}) \left(\frac{\text{Nm}^2}{\text{kg}^2}\right) \left(\frac{\text{J}}{\text{m}^3}\right) \left(\frac{\text{s}^2}{\text{m}^2}\right)} = 3.3835 \times 10^{-18} \sqrt{\left(\frac{\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}}{\text{s}^2 \cdot \text{kg}^2}\right) \left(\frac{\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2}{\text{s}^2 \cdot \text{m}^3}\right) \left(\frac{\text{s}^2}{\text{m}^2}\right)} =$$

$$3.3835 \times 10^{-18} \left(\frac{1}{\text{m} \cdot \text{s}}\right).$$

The real question is why would this be the case? Why is this field weakly present in all of space? Is that the result of the fact that some rapidly moving universe relative to our universe invoked a gravitomagnetic field? Another possibility is that our universe is like a spherical shell of radius R, carrying a uniform surface mass σ , is set spinning at an angular velocity ω . Using the magnetic vector potential at an arbitrary point in space, $B = \text{Curl}(A)$ for the magnetic field suggests that $B = \nabla \times A = \frac{2}{3} \mu_0 \sigma R \omega$. This is for the hollow case but maybe it should be made with better mass distribution, but in principle it seems possible that if our universe were rotating that would be where the centrifugal force is creating the constant gravitomagnetic field within the universe. Could the rotation of the universe if it were an observable bubble provide unnoticeable effects such as on earth? Is the rotation caused by something? Is the rotation why the galaxies are accelerating? I guess this makes sense if the reason the big bang happened in the first place was the elastic collision of the singularity of this universe with another singularity such that there was a recoiling of the first singularity by the second singularity and this caused not only singularity 1 our universe to be imparted with translational but rotational velocity, so as the singularity is expanding, (and another question is in what scaling because a scaling can always be chosen so that the events within the boundary of the universe appear to be a infinitesimal point or a singularity. The concept of singularity is indeed relative but nonetheless, the result of the elastic collision where the collision happened in such a manner that it was a field effect deflection and non direct impact of the boundaries of the universes since they were both singularities and so small that the boundary is infinitesimally small. It is potentially possible as well that the perceived collision we discussed here is with a virtual singularity in a virtual universe but that the virtual singularity is the carrier essentially of the force field and maybe this force field exists because instead the universe resides in a sea of other universes. Since it is unobservable the best we can do for now is make inferences about

Are we inside a rotating exploding black hole that exploded when the singularity of the universe exploded where the boundary of our universe is merely the perceptual boundary of our local perception, the Schwarzschild radius of the black hole? How could a black hole get to this size? But to answer this question brings to the honest forefront of how do we even know that this is large? How, if indeed this is the boundary of our perception can we be certain that indeed there does not exist a sea of universe that belongs to THE universe that contains bubbles of other universes in some parts, simply regular space such as nebulae in others and galaxies and such in others? What if there is a sea of constantly dynamically moving other universes of stuff that just goes endlessly beyond that perceptual boundary? To me, it is unfathomable that the universe, in our known observable bubble, can represent all that which there is. Yes, is is a lot, there are trillions upon trillions upon trillions of stars and the distance is vast, but when you bring into scope the true concept of infinity and step beyond the boundary of what you can possibly see, one must ask is it true that all which I known and the vast largeness of the numbers I know to be large is it possible

indeed that there exist an infinity beyond every which infinity which I break that brings me certainty? The thought of this is dread invoking it is existential fear invoking that the vastness of the universe is out of comprehension because it feels like it is always within grasp with just a bit more work and a bit more time.

There would always be a small gravitational effect that maybe if written with biot savart law can be shown how when the radius of the galaxy is significant enough from the sum of all the field to be able to plot the gravitoelectromagnetic contributions from the expanding universe. Using the same method as before the Newtonian approximation to relativity is the GEM equations which includes the density profiles and relationships to electromagnetic theory. The fundamental theory comes in here then to show that the apparent increase in mass comes from the gravitomagnetic energy. As the distance increases Is it possible that the magnetic field is the imaginary components of the space-time and the squaring of the field gives the needed negative energy? The universe apparently meets the Schwarzschild constraints in the sense that mass contained within the boundary of the observable universe at radius R would make it look like the universe is a giant black hole since the radius. Show that this is true for our universe using the correct numbers.

Energy is radiated away from the boundary of the observable universe in the same way that energy is radiated from the boundary of a black hole. Is the universe the result of a collapsing universal black hole?

Discussion:

The fact that this method shows that the galactic rotation curve phenomena for at least disk galaxies might be explained by the additional space-time or gravitomagnetic terms in the Newtonian case such as MOND suggest that Dark Matter may not be matter at all but may behave like matter by affecting matter with seemingly mysterious forces from the usual effects that are well known from Maxwellian electrodynamics. The electric field is a Harmonic function because it can be defined by the Maxwell wave equation after uncoupling the Maxwell equations. The gravitational field also has this as the case. But when representing the electric field, in cases where velocity is present, it can be shown that a magnetic field is induced by the motion of the charge. The magnetic field however has been shown to be merely a relativistic phenomenon of the electric field. That is what seems to be happening here with the rotation curves of dark matter. The presence of velocity terms of the masses causes the gravitomagnetic field which is nothing more than the gravitational field with time dependent and velocity terms of the motion.

Expanding the general simulations to other types of galaxies and building the error functions to verify the relativistic corrections for each relativistic model compared to the Newtonian case could help us correct the bounds of the dark matter estimates if there are any remainder terms after the relativistic terms have been added to the Newtonian approximations. The force responsible can be visualized as the perpendicular magnetic field for the gravitational field. It can be visualized as the GEM field but the GEM equations would be wrong because they do not properly accommodate for the relativistic corrections.

In the viewpoint of mass as energy and space-time as an energy field it seems possible that the additional terms for the space-time affect the relative mass of the galaxies and that in the vicinity of these clusters which have been proven to have large gravitomagnetic components and that gravitational lensing is being distorted by the additional field terms. It is known that large

masses bend light but it is not known how the interaction of the velocity dependent terms in general may affect light. With this said, it seems possible with the relativistic theory of rotation curves that the light is interacting with the additional field terms in the sense that the mass relative to the passing light of the galaxies in the cluster is perceived differently than when it is far removed from that galactic source.

In this context, it is plausible that the interaction between this particular field component and electromagnetic radiation induces a lensing effect of greater magnitude than previously anticipated. To thoroughly evaluate the modified Newtonian theory within the framework of relativity, rigorous research and experiments are imperative. By positing this theory as a viable alternative to the existence of dark matter particles, the present work aims to inspire future investigations that delve into this novel perspective.

In conclusion, the extensibility of Einstein's theory is reassuring, particularly in the ease with which it accommodates extensions. Notably, the alignment of my theory with Einstein's facilitates problem-solving endeavors. Acknowledging the inherent challenge of adequately describing and communicating complex scientific concepts, this paper serves as a foundational summary of key points. It lays the groundwork for future expansions and equation derivations based on the assumptions derived from the research.

While recognizing limitations in current knowledge, the proposed method stands as a data analysis approach that furnishes essential data and rules for the theoretical framework. The delineated methodology offers a practical means to modify existing equations, particularly in the 2D and 4D cases, obviating the necessity for an ND case. The presented method serves as a valuable tool for data-driven analysis, enabling facile comparison of the effects under scrutiny through the examination of contribution magnitudes.

Learning from electrodynamics, electric currents induce magnetic fields. So in the gravitomagnetic case matter currents induce gravitomagnetic fields in the Newtonian approximation. In electrodynamics, it is clear that the magnetic field is nothing more than a relativistic effect of mass having a velocity or that there is the existence of matter currents in a vicinity. The modeling of the galaxy as a density function implies that as that density function rotates in time there is a large matter current. It seems that the matter current since it resides in space-time which has been proven to expand according to the Hubble Law could add up sizable induced gravitomagnetic forces from the rotation of galaxies within the universe with an assumed mass dependent gravitomagnetic force given by the Newtonian force law.

It is also possible that the effects unseen from the galaxies moving within the cluster and clusters moving in the super cluster have relative effects on the motions of galaxies as well which is obvious since some galaxies have been observed to collide and some even to move in a keplerian way around a supermassive center of a cluster.

Using the error function method force terms can be fitted to functions that can be used to determine flaws with theories. The stability conditions that the rotation curves must meet in order for the circular orbits to be had implies that there is some balancing force. The selection of the mathematical model used describes the details of this force. In one theory, if we remain the

fundamental laws the same it can appear like there is additional mass because the theory has no way to accommodate for the extra force terms so because the laws are assumed to be true, one must incorrectly assume that the system is more massive than it appears. Quite the opposite can occur in some cases as well. The selection of the mathematical model and the inherent assumptions are therefore intrinsically connected to the answers the systems of equations output. By equality of the electrodynamic case there must be cases beyond simply gravitational waves where the gravitomagnetic part of the curvature of space-time becomes non-negligible. When one considers that the apparently slow moving stars in a distant galaxy are traveling at a mere $200\text{km/s} = 200000\text{m/s}$ with stellar masses around $1.9 \times 10^{30}\text{kg}$, it seems to make sense how such a fast moving object could cause distortions in space-time that are not obvious but which analogous to an electron moving in circular orbit in a magnetic field, because there is an inward force, a stellar mass moving around a galaxy will induce a gravitomagnetic field which is in the opposite case of the electron here being held in circular motion, will act to induce a dark or quasi-stellar mass current that acts on the stellar mass. What is happening here appears to be the equality between the field effect and the existence of a particle since the existence of a particle of certain type implies the existence of a field of a certain type. The solution presented from the theory of gravitodynamics compared to the Newtonian theory implies the existence of extra force terms which can only be explained relative to the Newtonian system of equations with the introduction of new mass terms since the forces in this simple Newtonian case are created from mass. And with the direction of the force being negative relative to the system of equations in the Newtonian case, this implies that in order for the Newtonian case to be extended to match observations of the gravitodynamic case which indeed has an additional field and force, virtual or dark particles are required to be introduced to explain the gravitodynamic force. By equality of gravitodynamics to relativity in the case $v \ll c$, this implies that in order for the Newtonian case to be extended to match observations of the relativistic case which indeed has an additional field and force in the form of space-time distortion, virtual or dark particles are required to be introduced to explain the additional space-time force.

There might be a symmetry group formed from the relation between gravitodynamic cases and electrodynamic. The induction of the gravitomagnetic field induces the existence of a virtual or quasi or dark particle which is what is creating the gravitomagnetic field in this viewpoint. It can be shown that by alternate selection with the theory of relativity that the induced force is a remnant of the relativistic field effect of the stellar mass moving with sufficient velocity to create additional gravitational or space-time distortions.

The gravitomagnetic component of the space-time gravitational field tensor seemingly adds additional forces to the Newtonian differential equation defining the state of the system that upon initial calculations yields forces proportional to the dark matter forces in the extra galactic rotation curve cases. This paper further speculates on other theoretical possibilities which should be tested in a more comprehensive manner outside of the scope of this paper.

Conclusion:

This paper highlights the possibilities of dark matter to be explained within the framework of the weak field theory of relativity which is essentially gravitodynamics and sets up the equations

for the fields as well as produces the modified velocity equations for galactic rotation curves as well as the virial theorem.

Uncertainties

The relativistic forces from the scaling changes as the velocity increases might come into play even if they are small due to the large timelines that the astronomical events are taking place at but as there is a boundary of the universe because of the boundary of electromagnetic radiation and essentially the boundary of our perception, it becomes more and more apparent that the surrounding environment that we reside within has measurable effects on our observable universe even if we can not see outside of this small little bubble of a potentially infinite space that contains infinite more universe beyond the observational boundary.

Beyond:

This paper is but only the start of the required computations and work necessary to be done to fully establish what is responsible for the dark matter forces on the observed matter for the relativistic framework. The velocity equations must be verified and more density profiles need to be used. More accurate equations for the density profile of each type of galaxy need to be determined and these density profiles should be used to plot the fields for each of the different types of galaxies. This approach is more of a simple piece by piece approach to the problem using linear gravity but a relativistic solution for nonlinear cases in general should be established because it would lead to a better understanding of the dynamics within the models in relativistic scenarios. In other words this problem needs solved without the linearization we used to assume equivalence to the Maxwell equations of electromagnetism.

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